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UNESCO-IHE INSTITUTE FOR WATER EDUCATION

Floodplain Modelling using Remote Sensing Data under Land-Use Change in Ethiopia

Mehari G. Hiben

MSc Thesis WSE-HI.12-02
April 2012

UNESCO-IHE
Institute for Water Education

Floodplain Modelling using Remote Sensing Data under Land-Use Change in Ethiopia

Master of Science Thesis
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Delft
April 2012

The findings, interpretations and conclusions expressed in this study do neither necessarily reflect the views of the UNESCO-IHE Institute for Water Education, nor of the individual members of the MSc committee, nor of their respective employers.

This thesis is dedicated to my almighty God

Praise the Lord!

Abstract

Flood inundation models are useful tools for floodplain management as they can help predict and determine flood prone areas and therefore support a more appropriate land-use planning (such as afforestation, and soil and water conservation activities) and discourage human settlements in high risk areas. This information system can assist land-use and urban planners as well as local authorities in managing floodplain areas under significant environmental change, by proposing mitigation measures, set priorities, and assist policy development. In this research, Geographic Information System (GIS) is coupled with hydraulic modelling (HEC-RAS) to produce a flood map of the Fogera floodplain (the upper Blue Nile in Ethiopia) under different scenarios of land use change simulated via the SWAT modelling system. GIS provides a broad range of tools for determining areas affected by floods and for forecasting areas that are likely to be flooded (probabilistic).

The emergent accessibility of new space borne data has led to a shift from a data-sparse to a data rich environment for monitoring and modelling floodplain processes. Nonetheless, the full potential and the uncertainties associated with these worldwide data sets for floodplain management still needs to be explored. In this work, a one-dimensional open channel steady-state hydraulics model (HEC-RAS) is set up. To this end, Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital terrain model (DTM) is used as topographic input, while the satellite imagery from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) is used for model calibration and validation. Hydraulic models are affected by different sources of uncertainty. In this study, parameter and input uncertainty are explicitly taken into account and visualized via probabilistic floodplain maps. This better enables characterization and visualization of the flood hazard.

Secondly, a distributed hydrological SWAT model is set up. The model is calibrated from 2000 through 2005 and validated from 2006 through 2009 for both the Gumera and Ribb catchments, which revealed good efficiencies. Then, three scenarios of land use change are set to evaluate the effect of land use changes on flood inundation patterns. The first scenario is expansion of agricultural land, the second is expansion of dry land, and the third is urbanization. All the three scenarios lead to an augment in flood discharge. This is visualized in this study via probabilistic floodplain maps using HEC-RAS and GIS.

To perform the ensemble simulation a Monte Carlo sampling techniques is used (type of Generalized Likelihood Uncertainty Estimation (GLUE) methodology). In view of that, model performance, reliability and predictive uncertainties are critically discussed.

This research also attempts to contribute to the analysis of whether the current emergent accessibility of globally and freely available remote sensing data (e.g. TRMM, SRTM, MODIS) may allow the production of probabilistic floodplain maps in areas with scarce data or highly uncertain information (such as Ethiopia). The results seem to indicate that hydraulic models based on globally and freely available data might provide a reasonable performance under all sources of uncertainty.

Keywords HEC-RAS, GIS, SWAT, SRTM DTM, Model performance, Probabilistic flood maps, Uncertainty analyses, Satellite imagery, Flood modelling, Flood hazard, ensemble simulation, hydraulic model.

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List of Symbols

ALPHA_BF	Base flow alpha factor
ASTER	Advanced Space borne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer
BLAI	Maximum Leaf Area Index
CANMX	Maximum canopy storage [mm]
Ch_K2	Saturated hydraulic conductivity
Ch_N2	Manning's "n" value for the main channel
Cn2	Initial SCS (Soil Conservation Service) CN II (curve number two) value
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
CRWO	CROPLAND/Agricultural
CRDY	DRYLAND C
DREAM	Differential Evolution Adaptive Metropolis
DEM	Digital elevation model
DTM	Digital terrain model
ENTRO	Eastern Nile Technical Regional Office
ECMWF	European centre for medium-range weather forecasts
ESCO	Soil evaporation compensation factor
EVI	Extreme Value Type I
GIS	Geographic information systems
GLUE	Generalized likelihood uncertainty estimation
GRAS	GRASSLAND
GW_DELAY	Ground water delay
GW_REVAP	Ground water revap coefficient
GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur [mm]
HEC-RAS	Hydro-Logic Engineering Centres River Analysis System
LP3	Log Pearson Type III
LUP	Land use update
MLUE	Machine Learning Uncertainty Estimation
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MWEE	Ministry of Water and Energy of Ethiopia
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
PDF	Probability Density Function
RFE	Rainfall estimation
Rsp	Spearman rank-correlation coefficient
SAR	Satellite Synthetic Aperture Radar
SAVA	SAVANNA
SOL_AWC	Available water capacity of the soil layer
SOL_Z	Depth from soil surface to bottom of layer
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SHRB	SHRUBLAND
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
TRIMM	Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission
URMD	Residential-Med/Low Density
USA	United States of America
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USGS	United States Geological survey

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

What is flooding?

Flooding is a natural process, which may lead to catastrophic results if it coincides with the presence of a vulnerable object. For example, a flood disaster may occur when human settlements coincide with excessive rainfall events, rise of water levels, or dam breaks. This may occur once in a blue moon or frequently. Thus, the occurrence and severity of flood disasters depends mainly on the topography, climate, rainfall distribution, watershed, economy, and land use of a certain region (*Di Baldassarre and Uhlenbrook, 2012*).

Historically, floods have been intertwined with the livelihood of human beings in at least two ways. First, they have cherished and have facilitated the emergence of early civilizations along river banks as in Egypt and Mesopotamia, and second, they have been considered as evil acts or punishments from spiritual forces. Today, flooding is a broad term that includes flash floods, river floods, and coastal floods. Their negative effects are typically most severe in the poorest countries, where populations and governments are least able to deal with this scourge. In Ethiopia, chronic incipient environmental changes promoting flooding have been associated with lack of land use planning, poverty and non sustainable land use (*Moges, et al., 2010*).

In many ways the significance of floods is self-evident. It is reported that flood disasters account for about a third of all natural disasters in terms of their number and associated economic losses (*Barredo, 2007*). In addition, floods are responsible for over half of the deaths associated to all natural hazards. Moreover, there is the trend of an increasing number of deaths due to flood disasters, which is also reflected by the attention given to flooding by the international media. We are often made aware of serious floods that lead to significant losses of life in one part of the world or another. For example, in recent years there have been catastrophic floods in Bangladesh, China, Mozambique, the USA, Poland, and Czech Republic, to name just a few countries. There is a global concern that climate change will lead to more frequent floods (*Bronstert, 2003*). The development of the flood is subject to physical processes that although complex are reasonably well understood. However, the processes form a complicated physical system of catchments and river networks and it is the need to understand and predict or forecast the generation and propagation of a flood in such a system that has given rise to the extensive use of computer simulation (*Douben, 2006*).

Hence, this thesis aims to predict floodplain inundation patterns under different scenarios of land use change. Accordingly, hydrologic and hydraulic models will be used to give an indication for decision and policy makers to be able to think seriously and analyse the potential consequence of flooding.

Finally yet importantly, it aims to explore and understand the use of globally available and freely distributed remote-sensing data to allow considerable progress in the field-scale application and testing of flood extent models. A practical example derived from satellite synthetic aperture radar (SAR) sensors have been used to evaluate and compare different

hydraulic models (Horritt and Bates, 2002; Horritt et al., 2007) as stated by Di Baldassarre and Schumann (2010).

1.2 Problem Identification

The Blue Nile is the major source of the Nile, and has its origins in Lake Tana located in the north-western Ethiopian highlands. Lake Tana is surrounded by sub-basins with a total area of 12,005 km² and drained by eleven major rivers (Assefa, et al., 2008). These major rivers include the Gilgel-Abay, Magech, Ribb and Gumera. The Gilgel-Abay flows in the north direction to the lake, the Magech flows to the south through the floodplains of Dembya, and the Ribb and the Gumera flow through the Fogera floodplains.

Figure 1 shows some of the catchments, hydrological stations, and wet lands of floodplain areas around Lake Tana including the case study of this research.

Ethiopia Study Area

Figure 1 Flooded woreda around Lake Tana
[Source: adopted from ENTRO ,2010]

A lot of research has been done on this area. Some of which has been carried out on precipitation forecasting for hydrologic rainfall runoff prediction (*Gizaw, 2011*), some on flood controlling under regulatory operations of planned reservoirs (*Surafel, 2011*), some of them are on flood forecasting and early warning (*Assefa, et al., 2008*), and some on flood hazard and risk assessment in Fogera wereda using GIS and remote sensing (*Gashaw and Legesse, 2011*). The main reason behind this extensive research is due to the fact that the Fogera floodplain has experienced many severe flood disasters.

Fogera is an administrative district name; locally it is called wereda. It is one of the most flood prone areas in the country. Whenever there is heavy rain fall in the watershed of Fogera wereda there is always flooding in the floodplain (*Assefa, et al., 2008*). Based on the 2007 national census conducted by the Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia (*CSA*) this woreda has a total population of 228,449. With an area of 1,111.43 square kilometres, Fogera has a population density of 205.55, which is greater than the zone average of 145.56 persons per square kilometre (*CSA, 2007*). This is also another clear message that the growth of population to more than the average number of persons per square kilometre has another impact on flooding with land use change. Furthermore, assessment of flood routing models and data in the Ribb river which was focused on analysis of data reliability in a data poor situation and the influence of assumptions made in models developed to understand the behaviour of the system (*Abebe and Werner, 2010*). The main objective of the study was to assess the reliability of the available data through careful analysis and modelling by combining together hydraulic flood routing models and data from the limited observation sites.

All the above-mentioned research has produced some modelling results. Nevertheless, some more research is still needed so as to improve the reliability of the models by reducing the uncertainties associated with data limitations. This necessitates the contribution of some development of floodplain modelling under land-use change using global remote-sensing data.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The objective of this research is to fill some gaps in the previous and future research in the area with three major aims.

- To improve our ability to model the Fogera floodplain by using satellite observations of flood inundation extent as tools to calibrate and validate the hydraulic model
- To evaluate flood hazard under different land use change scenarios
- To quantify and represent the uncertainties associated to the hydrodynamic modelling via probabilistic floodplain maps

1.4 Research questions

1. How valuable is the use of satellite imagery under uncertainty for hydraulic model calibration and validation?
2. How does flood extent vary as the result of land use changes?

2 Literature review

2.1 Flooding

Flooding is under study by many scientists that aim to take into account all the complexities of natural and human flood system. Dealing with, or speaking of floods means speaking of one of the issues on the global agenda because of its natural complexity and omnipotent reach, or touch to everyone in the world. We cannot completely avoid flooding. However, it is possible to learn how to live with flooding by optimizing the techniques that are developed by human beings. This is mainly done to avoid its catastrophic effects and devastating nature by reducing fatalities, which are mostly in developing countries, and economical losses mostly in developed countries (*Venkatachary, et al., 2001*).

2.1.1 Cause of Flooding

A flood is a hydrological event, which can be caused by heavy rainfall (or snow melt) and high discharge and/or high water levels that can pave the way to inundation of land adjacent to streams, rivers, wetlands, lakes and other water bodies. Flooding occurs when streams and channels are unable to convey the amount of water that has been generated through the rainfall-runoff process and as a result, there will be over bank flow and inundation of floodplain areas. Flood events may also happen due to the inability of water to escape downstream because of high water levels in the receiving or conveyance channels. Other causes can be snowmelt, long-lasting rainfall, failure of a dam or embankment, earthquakes, landslides, ice jams, high tides, storm surges, rising groundwater and so on (*Douben, 2006; De Wrachien, et al., 2011*). Furthermore, flood disasters are exacerbated by population changes leading to urbanization, changes of agricultural land, new infrastructures that might increase the frequency and severity of flooding.

2.1.2 Effect of Flooding

The impacts of flooding in nature particularly in human beings are short and long-term mental and emotional distress i.e. a feeling of extreme unhappiness and suffering from problems caused by a lack of money, food etc. In addition to this, acute and chronic diseases from water-borne pathogens attack the inhabitants of the affected area. For example, during an extreme flood event, there will be a contamination of the silt with sewer discharges, and in hotter climates, the lack of clean water during floods and the exposure to water-borne diseases can be very serious for the health of the survivors. This bad situation becomes worse and worse because of the fact that the situation creates an environment, which makes it impossible to reach the victims with emergency supplies. Furthermore, death occurs from the inability to escape from the flood (*Hajat, et al., 2005*)

The economic impact of flooding is again another effect, which brings about a total loss of some activities or economical developments in the affected area and its surrounding economic links. The other thing is individual impacts of flooding; these are measured by financial losses through damage to personal or business assets, loss of employment, loss of

crops and livestock, and inability to sell property in a flood-affected area, etc (*Veen and Logtmeijer, 2005*)

Finally yet importantly, I would like to stress that flooding questions the livelihood of human beings. Therefore, we have to deal with it, take care of it, and try to be able to optimizing living with floods by doing a lot of research on flood issues.

2.2 Hydrological and Hydraulic Models for Flood Mapping

Under the sub title it is important to discuss why we need flood modelling, why do we need a hydrological model? Why hydraulic model?

First and most of all, let us define the more general word that represents both hydrology and hydraulics i.e. the model. In other words, what is the reason or pretext for modelling? When should a model be used? The word model is used in many different contexts. So how can we develop a safe reliable model within water science engineering?

In order to answer these questions it is better to think in terms of information and the way we are going to handle and manage it (*Nunes Correia, et al., 1998*).

In all walks of life we are living in an unpredictable world, especially when we see it from the point view of natural hazards like flooding. Hence, it is impossible to put the whole world in a laboratory in which we can make experiments to see the catastrophic effect of the natural disaster. Therefore, we need the water science engineering models; this is again, called the mathematical modelling approach in which generic algebraic, ordinary or partial differential equations are solved analytically. In addition to this, a numerical model which is an approximation of a mathematical model and a computational model is an implementation of a numerical model on a computer system which are all derived on the bases of mathematical modelling to generate new understanding or knowledge and insight about how the flow behaves under different conditions. In general, models are representations of reality, and therefore, the results are not always accurate. However, they can be useful when they are interpreted using professional expertise. I would like to stress the contention by Abbott that "A model is a collection of signs that serve as a sign" (Abbott) as stated by Price (*2011*).

2.2.1 Hydrological Models

As explained in the context of modelling above, hydrological models are models of water science engineering that are used for representing the system behaviour by making comparisons of simulated and observed variables. Comparisons are, made between simulated and measured stream flow at the catchment outlet. After this, a validation of models is done to see the general model performance. Efficiency criteria are always done to make an objective assessment of the simulated and observed variables closeness to one another. These are like objective function graphs flow and hydrograph comparisons, flow residual graphs, statistical assessment measures, and sensitive parameters (*Krause, et al., 2005*). Figure 2 shows the typical example of a hydrological process. Where the hydrologic process describes the continuous movement of water on, above and below the surface of the Earth. Water can change states among liquid, vapor, and ice at various places in the water cycle. Although the balance of water on Earth remains fairly constant over time, individual water molecules can come and go, in and out of the atmosphere. This show the complexity of hydrological cycle where water moves from river to ocean, or from the ocean to the atmosphere, by the physical processes of evaporation, condensation, precipitation, infiltration, runoff, and subsurface flow.

Figure 2: A typical example of hydrological process

2.2.2 Hydraulic Models

The context of modelling described above in Section 2.2 also holds true for hydraulic models. These models of water science engineering are commonly used to describe the complexity of flow hydraulics taking in to account some or all the physics of the system according to the purpose, time, cost and other so many factors. For example, in the case of flooding according to the importance of the model and economy, the hydraulic model can be 1D, 2D, or 3D. In any hydraulic model two types of equations must be solved these are mass continuity (conservation of mass), and energy equation (water gains or losses energy as it moves through the system). Solving these equations is not terribly difficult if there is a single continuity equation and an energy equation. However, in a system we have thousands of these equations. Therefore, it is impossible or unthinkable to solve this problem by hand. Therefore hydraulic models can give us a solution to this problem which enables hydraulic engineers to design their structure and prepare an alternative plan for decision support (*Tung and Mays, 1981*).

The ultimate aim of this research is to produce an inundation map of flood prone areas. Therefore, a hydraulic model is a key to solve and show the inundation maps under different scenarios of stream flow or flood events (*Takeuchi, 2010*).

2.3 Remote sensing data

First, what is data? Data is information that can be collected from different sources stored and used especially on a computer (*Nilakanta and Scamell, 1990*). In general, models are

computer representations or scientific descriptions of data and modelling systems (software). Hence, without enough data it is impossible to build a model. Therefore, the importance of remote-sensing data is to a very great degree to discuss critically all the opportunities for improving flood-modelling; this is commonly afforded by the globally and freely available space-borne remote-sensing data. In addition to this, a new data source of remote sensing of higher resolution is available. Taking all this into account leads to the use of this remote-sensing data in a future research agenda to assist the scientific basis of flood issue research so as to bring about integrated flood management (*Di Baldassarre and Uhlenbrook, 2012*).

Hence, this kind of data is quite important, especially in developing countries that have less or no data measurements like the area where this research is going to be addressed. For example, in the area where there are no flood mark measurements it is quite help-full to calibrate and validate hydraulic models using uncertain satellite observations of flood extent (*Di Baldassarre, et al., 2009*).

2.3.1 Digital Elevation/Terrain Models (DEM/DTM)

The idea of DEM/DTM is as part of the data for the modelling system, which is the topography, and it plays a critical role in the distribution flux of water, energy and all the complexity of the terrain landscape. The innovation of this new data source of remote sensing is playing a significant role in bringing about new and smart ways of describing elevation data to create or produce DTM's. Therefore, the automated extraction of topographic parameters and information from DTM is a very important alternative in saving time, money, and energy to the manual evaluation and interpretations from the traditional survey. Hence, the development of this new data source is increasing the quality, resolution, and coverage from time to time (*Finlayson and Montgomery, 2003*).

2.3.2 Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)/ Advanced Space borne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) DTM

The SRTM mission has a horizontal resolution of 3-arc sec (approx. 90m). However, this horizontal resolution is of 1 arc sec (approx. 30m) and has been only released over the United States (*Pierce, et al., 2006*). In general SRTM represents the best quality space-borne, and freely available DEMs worldwide (*Roth, et al., 2002*). In contrast to the short duration of the SRTM mission, the ongoing ASTER is continuously collecting elevation information with a horizontal resolution of 15 m (*Nikolakopoulos, et al., 2006*).

Extensive ground-truth data, such as sets of flood marks, discharges, rainfall etc. Were, collected to verify the SRTM DEMs even though there was not enough data to verify the complete validation. Hence the performance requirements for the SRTM data products are:

1. The linear vertical absolute height error shall be less than 16m for 90% of the data.
2. The linear vertical relative height error shall be less than 10m for 90% of the data.

Table 1 below shows the SRTM performance observed by comparing with the ground water truth data. From this, it can be, proved that the SRTM met the performance requirements (*Rodriguez, et al., 2006*). From this point of view, the vertical height error of the topography data is extremely significant for hydraulic modelling. Therefore, the application of hydraulic modelling using SRTM DTM should be tested; nevertheless it meets the performance requirements (*Fujita, et al., 2008*).

Table 1 Verification of SRTM DTM

	Africa	Australia	Eurasia	Islands	N.America	S.America
Absolute Geo location Error	11.9	7.2	8.8	9.0	12.6	9.0
Absolute Height Error	5.6	6.0	6.2	8.0	9.0	6.2
Relative Height Error	9.8	4.7	8.7	6.2	7.0	5.5
Long Wavelength Height Error	3.1	6.0	2.6	3.7	4.0	4.9

[Source: adopted from An Assessment of the SRTM Topographic Products Yan (2011)]

Therefore, the idea of this SRTM/ASTAR literature is to see the different options of space born freely available DEMs to use the best option for the specific problem that is needed to be solved.

Absolute Error: Absolute error is the amount of physical error in a measurement, period let's say a meter stick is used to measure a given distance. The error is rather hastily made, but it is good to $\pm 1\text{mm}$. This is the absolute error of the measurement. That is, absolute error = $\pm 1\text{mm}$ (0.001m). **Relative Error:** Relative error gives an indication of how good a measurement is relative to the size of the thing being measured. Let's measure two objects with a meter stick. One measures a 5 meters $\pm 1\text{mm}$ and the other one measure a 1 meters $\pm 1\text{mm}$. The comparative accuracy of these measurements can be determined by looking at their relative errors i.e. relative error is absolute error over the value of thing measured i.e. $0.001/1=0.001$ and $0.001/5=0.0002$. Therefore, the relative error of 5 meter stick is considerably smaller than the relative error in the 1 meter stick.

2.3.3 Satellite Image

A satellite image is the way or the process of transforming large quantities of multispectral radiometry to synthesize or represent the landscape from satellites. When the content of the spatial resolutions increases, the quality of the transformation of the multispectral is higher. Therefore the better the simulation of the spectral content at the enhanced resolution, the more accurate the classification of mapping purposes (Wald, et al., 1997). This research concerns the issue of the flood events and their effect in flood-prone areas of Ethiopia. However, there is a very little data to deal with flood management. Therefore, the powerful and new emergent of remote-sensing tool is very useful for supporting hydraulic modelling and flood management. Furthermore, this tool is, needed to evaluate the model performance under uncertainty using this satellite imagery. Of course, there is a difference in resolution of this satellite imagery all over the world. In particular, high resolution radar imagery or areal topography of flood are only ever obtained occasionally, and the low orbit revisit times (35 days for ERS, 7-10 days for RADARSAT) of typical sensors, high quality data are available only at a limited number of sites globally (Schumann, et al., 2010). As a conclusion the higher the resolution, the better the representation of the system and the better one can represent the spatial variability in the model. However, the higher the resolution the lower the revisit time.

The Dartmouth Flood Observatory (DFO) provides a MODIS image for the case study area. MODIS is significant in water resource and flood management because of its high-spectrum resource, short observation periods and of course it is free of charge (Wu, et al., 2009). Hence, this satellite imagery is going to be used for the hydraulic model calibration and validation. Accordingly, the following figure 3 shows the image taken on 14th and 19th of August 2006 <http://www.dartmouth.edu/~floods/2006174Nile.html>.

Figure 3: The Fogera flood plains from MODIS satellite imagery
[Source: adopted from <http://www.dartmouth.edu/~floods/2006174Nile.html>]

2.4 Flood Inundation Mapping

Under this subtitle, it is critical to know why flood inundation process need to be mapped. There are two major reasons to undertake flood inundation modelling.

- It is an alternative to laboratory experiments or field data to enhance understanding of the processes involved in floodplain flow.
- To obtain a qualitative and quantitative results and predictions, this is to improve the management of floodplain areas. For example, by providing a flood risk, flood hazard, and flood vulnerability maps (qualitative), and the value of discharge, water surface elevation, inundation extent and flow velocity (quantitative) (Di Baldassarre, et al., 2010)

To give some clarification of the above terminologies, flood maps are very useful tools to represent spatial distributions of flood for flood management. Flood hazard maps show the intensity of the flood and their consequences with different return periods. Flood vulnerability maps illustrate the flood consequence on society, the ecological environment and the economy. Last but not the least is the flood risk map, which shows the special distributed risk, which is defined by the consequences multiplied by its associated probability that a given event will occur (Di Baldassarre, et al., 2010). Hence, these model results have a supportive, better and direct impression of flood inundation mapping. In addition to this,

flood maps are valuable for representing signals and giving a clear message and warning of flood events for the society and stakeholders (Merz,et al., 2007).

2.4.1 Deterministic Approach

In a deterministic approach, flood inundation maps show the flood extent without consideration of the inherent uncertainties associated with the modelling exercise (precipitation, stream-flow, topographic-representation, modelling-parameters and techniques, and geospatial operations).Therefore it is unknown how these uncertainties are transferred and propagated to the inundation map (Merwade,et al., 2008). This is because the deterministic approach is based on the assumption that the model fully represents the physical behaviour of the river.

2.4.2 Probabilistic Approach

In a probabilistic approach, flood inundation maps show the flood extent with an explicit visualization of the inherent uncertainty. These individual sources of uncertainty (precipitation, stream flow, topographic representation, modelling parameters and techniques, and geospatial operations) are known how they affect (the overall uncertainty) in the final flood inundation map based on the assumption that the model doesn't fully represents the physical behaviour of the river (Merwade,et al., 2008).

2.5 Uncertainty Analyses

2.5.1 What is Model Uncertainty

In simple terms, model uncertainty is when unknown quantities of Y on a basis of known quantities of X is based or dependant on the model M that tries to familiarize or encapsulate the assumptions that may be able to tie X and Y. In this regard, M has two parts. These are structural assumptions and parameters (Θ). The parameters (Θ) are dependent on the choice of the model structure (Draper, 1995). Therefore in general the concept of model uncertainty is our lack of sureness to describe qualitatively and quantitatively the exact situation in a system (Solomatine and Shrestha, 2009).

2.5.2 Sources of Uncertainty

In general, sources of uncertainty are related to the understanding and describing of the real world. The major sources are explained below.

- Perceptual model uncertainty, this is the conceptual representations of a system that is eventually or subsequently translated into the mathematical form in the model (AJ Abebe and Price, 2003;Solomatine and Shrestha, 2009). This is dependent on our individual expertise and therefore if this expertise is poor it may result in a highly uncertain model (Neuman, 2003).
- Data uncertainty, in this case uncertainty might be due to error in the measurement of input or output data. In addition to this when there is less data and an attempt to extrapolate from these data there might be higher uncertainty. Furthermore if there are missing data filling this data might have also another higher uncertainty (Neuman, 2003).
- Parameter estimation uncertainty, this is mainly the inability to accurately measure the model parameters. Direct expert, expert assessment, or the result of model calibration can do measurements. However all of these carry a lot of uncertainties with them (Neuman, 2003).

- Model structural uncertainty, this is the representation of the complex system in a simplified way with a lot of ambiguity in a computer (Heuvelink, 1998; Solomatine and Shrestha, 2009). In addition to this a high uncertainty in representing the state of the system at the start of the model is extremely significant (Liu and Gupta, 2007).

2.5.3 Uncertainty Analyses for Simple and Complex Models

Under this sub title, it is very important to discuss the idea of model uncertainty according to the different sources of uncertainty with respect to model complexity. The idea is explained graphically below to show how it is possible to decrease the amount of uncertainty by taking the optimal point that compensates or makes a balance between simple and complex models to minimize the model error. This helps the modeller to decrease the uncertainty of the model he/she built.

Figure4: Dependency of various sources of uncertainty on the model complexity
[source: adopted from Solomatine and Shrestha, 2009]

2.5.4 Estimation Methods of Uncertainty

The selection of uncertainty estimation methods is, always influenced by the source of uncertainty that has been chosen. It is stressed by Solomatine (2009) that the uncertainty estimation method should take in to account the objectives below:

- Identification and quantification of the source of uncertainty
- Reduction of uncertainty
- Propagation of uncertainty through the model
- Quantification of uncertainty in the model out puts
- Application of the uncertain information in the decision-making process

For the case of this research, parameter and input data uncertainties will be discussed. This is because; the aim of this research is to show how this uncertain parameters and input data sets are propagated throughout the model under the uncertain remote-sensing data or satellite imagery in flood inundation maps.

2.5.5 The Monte Carlo method

The most popular methods that are used for hydraulic and hydrological modelling are random sampling based methods (Monte Carlo simulation) (*Blasone, et al., 2008*). Hence, an analytical method is not an easy task to implement on physically based hydraulic models because of their complex computer-based. Monte Carlo simulation methods are a class of computational algorithms that rely on repeated random sampling to compute their results. Monte Carlo methods are a simple sampling of probability often used in simulating physical and mathematical systems. Because they are dependent on repeated computation of random or pseudo-random numbers, these methods are mainly suited to computation by a computer and are likely to be used when it is unachievable or impossible to compute a correct result with a deterministic algorithm (*Douglas and Gupta, 2007*). The model is run by taking into account all the values of uncertainty variables, as input and a group of model results is the output.

It is praiseworthy to note that the error of probability density function (PDF) is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of simulations in MC simulation. In other words, increasing the number of simulations will decrease the error. Therefore, it is computationally exhaustive to get the results with high accuracy. The MC simulation is able to stop randomly at any level of accuracy. Furthermore, unlike other uncertainty estimation methods it does not require as many assumptions or user inputs. However, the MC method becomes worse from two major practical limitations: (1) it is complicated to sample the uncertain variables from their joint distribution unless the distribution is well approximated by a multi-normal distribution (*Kuczera and Parent, 1998*) and (2) it is computationally unaffordable for complex models. On the subject of methodology of uncertainty sources, Monte-Carlo type methods are widely used for parameter uncertainty, the Bayesian methods and/or data assimilation can be used for input uncertainty and Bayesian model averaging method is suitable for model structure uncertainty (*Solomatine and Wagener, 2011*).

2.5.5.1 GLUE

Generalized likelihood uncertainty estimation (GLUE) is a sampling-based approach which can be seen as a particular case of Monte Carlo Simulation (*Beven and Binley, 1992*). GLUE discards the notion of an optimal parameter set of one model or best-fit model and just treats each model parameter or model structure as having an equal likelihood of being accepted (*Montanari, 2005*). A big size of number parameters is sampled based on uniform distribution. Every parameter set is fed into the model to get the simulation results, and all results are compared with the measured data (*Cameron, et al., 1999*). After that, it is analyzed and evaluated to select the parameter that has a major influence on the model and the trial model to be castoff.

One of the easiest and best application of GLUE to show how to calculate the likelihood weighted uncertainty bounds is given by (*Beven, et al., 2000*): Assume there is a river discharge of time t produced by n number of simulations, provide the results $Q_i(t)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$, and each $Q_i(t)$ has possessed its likelihood weight. Those likelihood weights were rescaled to produce a cumulative probability of 1. All $Q_i(t)$ are ranked in ascending order and

a probability of not being exceeded is assigned to all. Thus probability is expressed as the summed up rescaled weights of all the simulations which are smaller than this $Q_i(t)$, including $Q_i(t)$ itself. After that a cumulative function is constructed, and the $Q_i(t)$ with the largest likelihood weight is set to the highest probability in the distribution and the sum of all likelihood weight is set equal to the probability of 1. This allowed the uncertainty bound with a confidence interval to be assigned to the $Q_i(t)$ which had the same probability.

GLUE requires the user to decide which source of uncertainty should be considered subjectively. Making explicit treatment of a chosen uncertainty source does not guarantee that the other source of uncertainty has no influence on it. Different source of uncertainty are associated with one another. For instance, the uncertainties of model parameters are inflated by model structure and model inputs given by parameterize will be pretentious if model input data are far from the factual value.

2.5.5 Source of uncertainty to be modelled

The fundamental subject of GLUE is to make your mind up which source of uncertainty will be considered after the modelling purpose is set clearly.

Probabilistic techniques for uncertainty analysis often focus on parameter uncertainty (Solomatine and Wagoner, 2011). However, some the uncertainty associated to input data and model structure might be in some instances higher than parameter uncertainty. This is particularly true in the case of hydraulic models using freely and globally data as input. The input of low resolution of DTM brings large uncertainty that might considerably and adversely influence the model results.

Table 2 Importance of the model parameters for 1D flood inundation model

Parameter	Manning's floodplain	Inflow magnitude	Manning's channel	Theta	Manning's outflow
Importance	16.25	33.25	37.50	3.00	10.00

[Source: adopted from Pappenberger (2008)]

As an example, Table 2 indicates the significance of the model parameters in a one-dimensional flood inundation model, HEC-RAS, which was found by Pappenberger, *et al.* (2008). The percentage of importance is directly proportional to the impacts on model output. A good knowledge of understanding these model parameters has big advantage to reduce the uncertainties in the model output. Accordingly, Manning's n on channel and/or inflow magnitude was found to be the most significant sources of uncertainty.

2.5.5 Calibration and sensitivity analysis

Calibration is a method used to fine-tune model parameters to reduce the errors. These are deviations between model results and observations. In flood inundation modelling, the surface roughness parameters are usually selected for calibration and their values are changed manually or automatically, (Horritt and Bates, 2002). For instance, in statistics the root means squared error is one of the techniques that is used to asses and matchup model results with observed values. Nonetheless, the complexities of river hydraulics make the setting of the objective function for hydrodynamic flood modelling a tricky job. 1D and 2D models of flood hydraulics (HEC-RAS, LISFLOOD-FP and TELEMAC-2D) were tested on a 60 km

reach of the river Severn, UK, using floodplain and channel friction as free parameters, against both the observed inundated area and records of downstream discharge for flood events in 1998 and 2000 (*M. S. Horritt and Bates, 2002*). The predictive power of the models calibrated against inundation extent for one event could thus be measured using independent validation data for the second event. The results demonstrated that for this reach both HEC-RAS and TELEMAC-2D models can be calibrated against discharge or inundated area data set and gave good predictions of inundated area, while the LISFLOOD-FP needs to be calibrated against independent inundated area data to produce acceptable results. Therefore, unlike the predictive Performances of models depends on the objectives of the case study area, Sensitivity of the model results and reliability of observed data.

Sensitivity analysis is a prerequisite of model calibration and is often performed by changing the values of one or more parameters or input data at a time (*Hall, et al., 2005*). This helps to decide which parameter or input data has an overriding effect on the model results, and to appreciate its trustworthiness. In common, hydrologic and hydrodynamic models are sensitive to DEM resolution, surface roughness, initial and boundary conditions, and numerical parameters as well (*Haile, 2005*).

Consequently, a 1D/2D hydrodynamic model was, used to know the dynamics of flows in the floodplain to verify the flood extents/ inundation depths by taking into account the issues of uncertainties and sensitive parameters (*Prestininzi, et al., 2011*).

2.6 Previous studies

Some research works was done in the Fogera floodplain to weigh up the cause of flooding and its consequences (*Sileet, 2005*). From those studies, one was, carried out by TROPICS and Shebelle Consulting Engineer's PLC, which mainly focuses on flood risk mapping for pilot areas in Ethiopia. These studies were, contracted by the Eastern Nile Technical Regional Office (ENTRO) to perform a flood risk assessment for flood plains surrounding the Lake Tana in Ethiopia. This report shows that the Eastern Nile region is particularly vulnerable to these frequent and damaging floods, causing significant loss of life and economic damages. In addition to this in Ethiopia, recent floods have been particularly severe. The World Food Program reports that the 2006 Ethiopian floods in eastern and southern Ethiopia affected over 70,000 people, including 16,000 displaced, and over 600 dead (*Gashaw and Legesse, 2011*). The summer 2007 floods were, reported to be equally devastating, causing severe flooding in the regional states of Amhara and Gambella, affecting over 60,000 people and destroying farmlands, road, and homes.

The other studies were done on flood forecasting and early warning decision tools to battle the recent flood nuisance (*Assefa, et al., 2008*). This study conducted an ensemble flood forecasting analyses by making use of different quantitative precipitation forecast (QPF) using the HEC-HMS rainfall runoff model. As the extension of this research one on Precipitation forecasts for hydrologic rainfall runoff predictions (*Gizaw, 2011*), some on flood hazard and risk assessment in fogera wereda using GIS and remote sensing (*Gashaw and Legesse, 2011*), and some on flood controlling under regulatory operations of planned reservoirs (*Surafel, 2011*). The main reason behind this extensive research is that the Fogera floodplain has been experiencing many severe flood disasters (*Verdin, et al., 2005*).

Nevertheless, this research outlines the importance of remote sensing data for the calibration and validation of a hydrodynamic model. Furthermore, this research aims at making an

ensemble simulation of flow to produce a probabilistic floodplain map in the Fogera floodplain using a 1D HEC-RAS model and a GIS extension HEC-GeoRas for floodplain mapping. GIS application is also used to produce probabilistic flood maps where predictive uncertainty of parameters and inputs are explicitly discussed. In addition to this, a SWAT model is built to produce a rainfall runoff hydrological model to produce the likelihood of flood extent under scenarios of the land use change. These combinations and the probabilistic approach make this research new from the previous studies.

In general, this research is mainly focusing on the modelling approach of floodplains by combining both the hydrological the hydrodynamic models by combining SWAT with HEC-RAS. Finally yet importantly, to make this research fruitful and complementary the previous research in the area has made a great contribution starting from data source and goes through understanding some of the flooding characteristics in the study area.

3 Study area and data description

The Gumara and Ribb catchments are the main two watersheds in the upper Blue Nile and drains to the Lake Tana. These watersheds have a length from its shore of Lake Tana to the foothills of Debre Tabor Mountain and share a common water divide line. The data used for this research were obtained found from the Ministry of Water Resource, National Meteorological of Ethiopia, NBI, ENTRO and previous research done on the study area.

3.1 Study area description

3.1.1 General

The Lake Tana sub-basin is an element of the upper Blue Nile in Ethiopia. These major rivers include the Gilgel-Abay, Magech, Ribb and Gumera. The Gilgel-Abay flows in the north direction to the lake, the Magech flows to the south through the floodplains of Dembya, and the Ribb and Gumera flow through the Fogera floodplains. Figure 5 below shows Lake Tana and measure rivers drained to it.

The Ribb and Gumara rivers start off from the highlands of South Gonder. The Ribb starts from an elevation of approximately 4135 m amsl near the Guna Mountains while the Gumara starts off from an elevation of 3500 m amsl. These two rivers flow through the slope of the mountainous areas and finally attain a slope of 1/5000 while they arrive at the Fogera Floodplain. Therefore, the Fogera floodplain is always flooded during the heavy rainfall events of the rainy seasons of Ethiopia often from July through September.

The total catchment of the study area i.e. the Ribb and Gumara rivers is 1790km² and 1500 km² correspondingly. However, at the flow gauging stations the catchment area of the Ribb and Gumara is 1497 km² and 1239 km² respectively. Since the contribution of flooding from the catchments in the floodplain is trivial, therefore the upstream flow boundary condition for the floodplain modelling is assumed to be at the gauging stations where the outlet of the hydrological models is set.

The total river length of the Ribb and Gumara catchments is 105 km and 96 km on a 1:50000 scale map correspondingly. On the other hand, the flow of the Gumera River has higher discharge with the mean and maximum of 35m/s and 297m/s respectively. The Ribb River is 14m /s and 102 m /s, respectively. The following figure 5 shows flood and wet land areas around Lake Tana sub-basin. The topography of the study area is generally flat, with about 0.03% general slope and characterized by black cotton soils. There are small ponds and creeks (streams) in the Fogera plain (AAU, 2009). The site is mainly covered by small scattered villages; widely scattered trees and agricultural land (A.B. Abebe and Micha, 2010)

All the rainfall gauging stations are out of the Ribb basin while two gauging stations (Addis Zemen and Debre tabor) are on the basin of Gumara as shown in figure 6. This questions the reliability of the data to use for building a model. In addition to this, the Adis Zemen river gauge (Ribb basin) is not properly functioning during heavy rainfall it washed away or tilted/cut which is unable to measure the right level. These all revealed questioning of the reliability of the data, or in other words high uncertainty of ground data set in the area.

Figure 5 Flood and wet land areas around Lake Tana sub-basin
[Source adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

3.1.2 Topography, land use and land cover

The Lake Tana sub-basin contains a mixed topography of high mountains on rolling edges, flat grasslands and meandering streams (Kebede, et al., 2006). The eastern part of the sub-basin is surrounded by the Farta plateau that extends above 4000 m amsl at Guna Mountain. The altitude of the Farta plateau is between 2400 and 2600 m and is regarded as a relatively gentle slope and consistent topography in nature. The evolution between the Farta plateau and the Fogera plain is regarded as a rolling and non-uniform topography.

The plain areas extended to Lake Tana are highly subjugated by cultivated land and swamp. The cultivated land and swamps lands are used as a grazing territory in the waterless season. The Ribb and Gumara catchments are devoid of any forests except for a few trees and shrubs.

3.1.3 Climate, rainfall and temperature

According to the conventional classification of climatic zones in Ethiopia the climate of the Ribb and Gumara catchments, belong to the Woina-Dega zone (elevation 1800-2400 m amsl and mean annual temperature 16-20 °C). The rainfall period is often called monsoon in Ethiopia because it is, linked with a change in principal wind direction. In the dry season north-easterly winds prevail while westerly and south-westerly winds dominate the wet season. More or less all the Ethiopian highlands, as well as the study area take delivery of an annual rainfall of more than 1000mm (Assefa, et al., 2008). The study area receives ample rainfall during the wet season of July through September. This is allied with the Inter Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ). An in depth narrative is initiated in Babu (2002). Furthermore, the temperature in the study area varies from 18 through 20 °C while humidity varies between 58-80% from May through August.

3.2 Soil data

A GIS soil dataset containing information on soil group as per FAO classification was obtained from the Ministry of Water Resources of Ethiopia. The major soil groups in the study area are Luvisols, Leptosols, Litic leptosols and Vertisols. These soil groups have a widespread property of clay, with trivial properties of clay loam and silt clay (Appendix-B). This information in return made it possible to build the initial SWAT model parameters during the hydrological model development.

The following Figure 6 and 7 shows the land use class, watershed, meteorological stations, and slope classes of the case study.

Figure 6 Fogera Floodplain land use class source

[Source: adopted from MWEE see acronyms in XII]

Figure 7 Fogera Flood plain watershed and slope

[Source: adopted from MWEE]

3.3 Meteorological data

3.3.1 Rainfall

Ten years (2000-2009) of meteorological data were obtained and collected from the National Meteorological Agency of Ethiopia. The location of the meteorological stations is shown in Figure 7. According to NMA, meteorological stations are categorized into four classes. In Class I stations, meteorological parameters such as wind speed, sunshine duration, precipitation etc are recorded every three hours at 03:00, 06:00, 09:00, 12:00 and 15:00 GMT. In Class III, stations merely maximum and minimum temperature and total rainfall are recorded at 06:00 and 15:00 GMT while Class IV stations merely record daily rainfall at 06:00 GMT.

The daily rainfall data from 2000 through 2009 was offered to this study. This data was semi-analyzed data from the previous study (Assefa, *et al.*, 2008). The missing data was, filled by referencing class-1 stations at Gonder and Bahir Dar and a 0.25 ° x 0.25 ° grid TRMM data sources. Hence according to the Assefa (2008) investigation, the class-I source was not a reasonable source in view of the fact that these stations have missing data gaps in the same periods. However, the rainfall data from TRMM within a grid have more improved estimates for data filling than this class-I station. Indeed, it is difficult to bring to a close that TRMM performance has good bases than ground stations. Relatively it is used as an option method. The correlation of the daily and monthly time series data from TRMM are tabulated below in Table 3.

Table 3 TRMM correlation with ground station

Stations	R ² (daily)	R ² (Monthly)
Debre Tabor	0.38	0.79
Yufag and Wereta	0.41	0.81
Adis Zemen	0.36	0.78
Wereta and Wenzaye	0.39	0.80

[Source: adopted from Assefa (2008)]

3.3.1 Temperature and relative humidity

In the highlands of Ethiopia, temperatures are realistically warm and cool around the year but infrequently hot. As reviewed by Kebede (2006). The temperature variation all the way through the year is insignificant in the study area. It merely varies within the confines of 18 °C through 21 °C. The humidity in the study area is reported to vary between 58% and 80% from May to August, respectively (Assefa, *et al.*, 2008).

3.4 Hydrological data

We obtained the daily time series flow for both the Gumara and Ribb rivers with their individual channel cross-sections (Appendix-G) at both gauging stations. Hence, the physical location of the station, the river network system and sub catchment of both gauging stations are viewed from above.

This research uses the annual peak flows for flood frequency analysis in view of the fact that the peak flows are abundant in the wet seasons. In day-by-day historical flow records, there are many missing data identified from one month through four months (Table 4) which is quite difficult to fill in easily. Nevertheless, all these missed data gaps occur in the dry seasons of the year, and it is not obligatory or crucial to fill them in and analyze them for this specific research.

Table 4 Missing flow records of Gumara and Ribb rivers in dry seasons

Gumara gauging stations				Ribb gauging stations			
Starting date	Ending date	Year	NO. Missing	Starting date	Ending date	Year	NO. Missing
Oct-22	Nov-12	1989	21	Oct-29	Dec-12	1980	45
Jan-01	Apr-03	1998	93	Oct-01	Dec-31	1982	92
Dec-12	Mar-08	2000	58	May-05	Jun-30	1991	57

[Source: adopted from MWEE]

Furthermore, some missing records were also observed prior to 1992 as shown in Figure 8. However, after this year there are no missing data records. This can be recognized as shown below in Figure 8. Despite the fact that this research aims at event-based simulation, there is no need of filling the data gaps in the recession periods. The real flood events were recorded in 1966, 1996, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2003 and 2006 years (Wubshet, 2008). Of these flooding events, 2006 is further preferred and analyzed for model simulation because the availability of the satellite imagery, and meteorological and hydrological data.

Figure 8 Historical daily flows of the Gumara and Ribb rivers source
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

The peak flow recorded within the rainy season (Jul-Aug-Sep) is shown in Figure 9 and 10 below for both the Ribb and Gumara respectively. These peak flows are resulted from high rainfall distribution on each catchment. This is due to less infiltration capacity, because of high antecedent moisture due to the rainy season. Therefore, the catchment generates the highest amount of surface runoff. Whilst looking at the peak flows of the Ribb which are recorded in August (1994, 1996 and 1998), they are doubtful peak flow records as shown in Figure 9. This might either occur most probably due to the washing away of the staff gauges by or flood and reading the maximum flood marks merely. Otherwise, it might be because when the riverbank reaches at its full level, it overflows and distributes over the surface of the land, so the gauge shows more or less similar reading. However, avoiding these datasets from flood frequency analysis is not a good approach. Therefore, these datasets were included in the analysis but not considered for the model simulation.

Figure 9 Daily flow of the Ribb for the wet season source
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

Figure 10 Daily flow of the Gumara for the wet season source
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

3.5 Conclusions and discussions on data processing

This research adopted an event-based simulation technique. Therefore, exhaustive data processes were analysed on the annual peak flows, 27th of July to 16th of August 2006, which causes flooding in the Fogera Floodplain. The data was checked out for missing data. As a result, no missing data were observed. The data were also checked whether they have trends/ mean differences or not using the basic data screening procedures (Dahmen, et al., 1990). Results shown in Table 5 have no trends observed.

In conclusion, the hydrological and meteorological data records were used for farther studies such as frequency analysis and model set up.

It was also noticed that the Gumara watershed contributes higher runoff compared to the relatively higher Ribb catchment area. Above all the shape and catchment characteristics may result in such runoff discrepancies generated from each catchment. For that reason, the Gumara watershed has a semi-rounded shape with a smaller time of concentration yields and higher runoff at its outlet compared to the elliptical shape of the Ribb watershed having higher time of concentration (see Figure 6 above). In addition to this, the weighted spatial variation of the nearby and adjacent rainfall contribution of the Gumara watershed is much higher compared to those nearby rainfall stations which contribute to the Ribb watershed.

Table 5 Screened hydrological and meteorological data for trends source

Screened Data Rainfall Station, mm	Rsp	Student's t- Distribution	Degree of freedom (n-2)		Data Trend
			Min, 2.5%	Max, 97.5%	
Bahir Dar	-0.39	-1.89	-2.09	2.09	No
Wanzaye	-0.40	-1.95	-2.09	2.09	No
Woreta	-0.05	-0.23	-2.09	2.09	No
Debre Tabor	-0.13	-0.58	-2.09	2.09	No
Adis Zemen	0.04	0.18	-2.09	2.09	No
Yifag	0.09	0.44	-2.09	2.09	No
Flows, M3/s					
Gumara	0.33	1.55	-2.09	2.09	No
Ribb	0.33	1.54	-2.09	2.09	No

[Source: adopted from Surafel, 2011]

4 Methodology

4.1 Over all approach

Hydrological and hydraulic models will be used for the development of the probabilistic floodplain mapping. First, data are going to be collected both to build up the hydrological and hydraulic models. These data are mainly precipitation, discharge, temperature, land cover or use, soil, population growth, infrastructure and so on.

From the previous research in the same study area (*Assefa, et al., 2008*), there are some ground measured data available. These are discharge, precipitation and temperature from the period of 2000 through 2006 for all stations in the Ribb and Gumera catchments and, this research is aiming at adding some more data from 2007 through 2009. Therefore, this will help the research to have six years of data for model calibration and four years for model testing.

On top of this, precipitation and other hydrological data are scarce in the study area. It was observed that there are huge missing data gaps in many meteorological gauging stations located in the Lake Tana sub-basin (*Gizaw, 2011*). Remote-sensing freely available TRMM grid data, provided by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) will be used to get a better estimate of the rainfall in the study area where data is scarce. After having all these data available, the following general research procedure will be followed. The details are, explained phase by phase below:

- Phase-one: Hydrological model building

A hydrological model will be built calibrated and validated against the ground data. These will produce a hydrographs of current and future land use.

- Phase-two: Hydraulic model building

A hydraulic model will be built calibrated and validated against the satellite imagery.

- Phase-three: Ensemble Simulation

An ensemble simulation model will be carried out under the GLUE framework and the model performance will be evaluated.

- Phase-four: Probabilistic flood inundation mapping

A probabilistic flood inundation map will be produced using freely available remote-sensing data under the GLUE framework.

4.2 Modelling System

4.2.1 The hydrological model SWAT

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) for the rainfall runoff model is proposed; this tool is used mainly to see the impact of land use and land cover. The idea is to see and evaluate how the land-use changes will probably affect the forecasted situation in the study area and whether this likelihood has positive or negative impact in the floodplain.

SWAT is a modelling system, which is freely available and is extremely important for water resource professionals. It is a distributed parameter modelling system, necessary for basin-scale studies, which have large input data requirements. Geographic information systems (GIS) and model–GIS interfaces aid the efficient creation of input data files required by such models (*Jayakrishnan, et al., 2005*).

4.2.2 The Hydrodynamic model HEC-RAS

HEC-RAS modelling system was selected for the following reasons:

- Handles sub-critical, supercritical and mixed regime flows
- Solves 1D fully dynamic Saint-Venant equations using the implicit finite-difference method which has the advantage of being a more stable scheme than explicit numerical methods
- Handles the effect of flow over structures (in particular makes use of Hager’s lateral weir equation and has good functionality for lateral structures)

An additional benefit of selecting HEC-RAS is that the model can be expanded to include:

- Water quality analysis (using an explicit scheme for advection-dispersion)
- Sediment transport analysis
- Data storage and management
- Graphics, reporting and mapping

Last but not least are the GIS tools, Arc-GIS 9.3, which enable the user to process the satellite data (DTM projections and clips), and flood inundation maps. HEC-GeoRAS is a GIS extension that creates utilities for the preparation of GIS data to export in to HEC-RAS and generates GIS data from RAS output.

4.3 Work Flow Diagram

Figure11: Work flow diagram

5 Flood frequency analyses

A flood frequency analysis was performed to approximate flood flows for 2, 5, 10, 50 and 100-year periodic intervals in the Gumara and Ribb basins in the Lake Tana Region.

The main purpose of the flood frequency analysis of the hydrologic data is to speak about the magnitude of extreme events to their frequency of occurrence using the technique of probability distributions (*Chow, et al., 1988*). In addition to this, flood frequency analysis has the following two major functions. One is to predict the likelihood occurrence of flood amount over a certain period and the second one is to calculate approximately the frequency of floods manifesting.

There are quite a lot of methods conducting flood frequency analysis on time basis to estimate probabilities and return periods. Some of the methods are Normal, Lognormal, Extreme Values and Log-Pearson Type III Distributions. Nevertheless, Log-Pearson Type III (LP3) and Extreme Values (EVI) distributions are the most well liked and frequently used methods all over the world (*Surafel, 2011*). Hence, among others, these two approaches were chosen.

It is obvious that, before carrying out the flood frequency analysis, observed datasets were pre-Processed and checked for extremities using outlier guidance. An outlier is an observation that deviates much from other observations (*USGS, 1981*). This might be due to measurement error and/or statistical sampling problems. Identifying outliers and dealing with their uncertainties rely on understanding of the data and its sources (*Bayliss and Reed, 2001*). However, a serious attention should be given to the fact that their presence or removal from the population alters the statistics significantly.

5.1 General Methodology

For the flood frequency analysis, the Log-Pearson Type III (LP3) distribution and the Extreme Value Type I (EVI) distribution were built-in to the available peak flow data at the Gumara and Ribb gauges. A full description of the LP3 and EV1 distributions can be found in Chow (1988). The USGS computer program PeakFQ was used for the LP3 distribution statistical analyses (*ENTRO, 2010*).

5.1.1 Available Data Used in Analyses

Historic daily peak stream flow data were available as well as available collected data representing the historic peak lake levels of Lake Tana. These data are valuable for determining appropriate downstream boundary conditions for hydraulic model development. Analysis of the historic lake level data was therefore incorporated as part of this analysis. The available data represent formally recorded daily and instantaneous peak values, which apparently have already been through quality control procedures. Therefore, the data were not altered from their original form Table 6 summarizes the available data used in the flood flow development/frequency analyses

Table 6 Available data used in the flood flow development/frequency analysis

Point Name	Available Historic Period	Number of Daily Peaks Available	Number of Instantaneous Peaks Available
Gumara	1959-2003	43	14
Ribb	1959-2003	42	18
Lake Tana Level	1959-2003	-	-

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

From the computation, there are no outliers obtained. Results are, shown in Table 7 below. In conclusion, the annual maximum flow observations from the population datasets were then used for flood frequency analysis.

Table 7 Summarized result for Gumara and Ribb rivers observed flows

Flow	Observed data		Outliers/Threshold values		Skew Coefficient (CS)	
	Ribb	Gumara	Ribb	Gumara	Ribb	Gumara
Max	218.69	397.55	256.23	433.64	0.14	0.06
Min	57.80	156.58	49.75	135.20		

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

Figure12 shows a plot of the annual peak daily flow data available at the Ribb and Gumara gauges. The year-to-year variability of the Gumara measurements is large. In addition, measurements of the Ribb gauge have a decreasing trend from about 1974 and the variability in flow discharge magnitudes is lower than the variability at the Gumara gauge. It has been suggested that the rating curve used to estimate discharges from observed stages at the Ribb gauge underestimates flows that exceed the channel banks (ENTRO, 2010).

Figure 12 Daily peak stream flows at Gumara, Ribb and Megech gauge stations

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

As discussed above, the main objective of the flood frequency analysis is to relate the magnitude of flood events to their frequency of occurrence through probability distribution. The historical annual peak flow records of Ribb and Gumara Rivers shown in Figure 13 below.

Therefore, in Figure 13 shows some basic information with reference to annual maximum observed flows for more than the last 50 years and this data set is used in the frequency analysis. From the graphs, the peak flows are altering over time, either due to land use change, stream channel deformation or some other facts. Nevertheless, peak flows are highly variable and altered unevenly from year-to-year. For example, the Ribb river flows show a decreasing trend, below the average value since 1980 disparate to the Gumara flows.

On the other hand, even if flow data show a decreasing trend, the severity of the flood disasters has increased alarmingly since the mid of 1990's (ENTRO, 2010). There are different reasons for this apparent contradiction, such as the inaccuracy associated with the Ribb data and the fact that human activities driven by population growth have exacerbated flood risk.

Figure 13 Plots of annual peak stream flow on the Gumara and Ribb Rivers
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

5.1.2 Required Data Adjustments

Because the overall project goal is to map the maximum inundation extents for flood events of different return periods, the input data for the flood frequency analysis should represent the instantaneous maximum stream flow. As seen in Table 6, the bulk of the available data represents the peak daily average. For basins with times to peak of much less than 24 hours, the peak daily average is lower than the maximum instantaneous peak, which occurred during that day. Therefore, to translate these daily averages into instantaneous peak values the daily values were scaled upward by a peaking factor. In the two cases (Gumara and Ribb) peaking factors were determined by comparing the available instantaneous peak values to their corresponding daily average values. For each of these stations, the available peak daily average values were plotted against the calculated peaking factor to see if a relationship between the daily discharge magnitude

and the peaking factor value was evident. These plots are shown in Appendix-A. As seen on these plots, no clear relationships exist. Therefore, the average calculated peaking factor for each site was used to scale up the daily average values (for years where instantaneous values were not available) so that they approximate instantaneous peaks. Table 8 shows the peaking factors which were calculated or estimated and used for each location. The final adjusted flow time series were plotted for the Gumara and Ribb stations and are included in Appendix-A (ENTRO, 2010)

Table 8 Calculated/estimated peaking factors

Point Name	Peaking Factor
Gumara near Bahirdar	1.310
Ribb near Adis Zemen	1.296

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

5.1.3 Flood Flow Estimates using Log Pearson Type III and Extreme Value Type I Distributions

Estimates of flood flows, which give return intervals or probabilities of exceedance are required for the design of hydraulic structures and floodplain management.

Program PeakFQ performs statistical flood-frequency analyses of annual-maximum peak flows (annual peaks) following procedures recommended in Bulletin 17B of the Interagency Advisory Committee on Water Data (1982), referred to hereinafter as Bulletin 17B. The Bulletin 17B procedures treat the occurrence of flooding at a site as a sequence of annual random events or trials. The magnitudes of the annual events are assumed to be independent random variables following a log-Pearson Type III probability distribution; that is, the logarithms of the annual peak flows are assumed to follow a Pearson Type III distribution (USGS).

Therefore, the PeakFQ program was used to fit the LP3 distribution to the adjusted peak flow data for the Gumara and Ribb basins. Inputs to the program were built in the adjusted flow data and the station skewness. Preliminary results of the flood frequency analysis were developed from an estimate of a generalized skewness (arithmetic averaged of station skewness), because it has been found that a regional LP3 approach minimizes bias introduced by small samples (Bulletin #17, Interagency Advisory committee on Water Data, 1981) (Erman and Jones, 1996). However, peak flow estimates generated from the station skewness fluctuates only about 1.5% to 9.8% from the initial estimates. These discrepancies were considered small compared to the degree of uncertainty introduced by a regional analysis based on only four stations. Consequently, sample skewness was used in the final analysis (ENTRO, 2010). Table 6 lists the skewness of the stations.

Table 9 Sample skewness (sample data includes the peaking factor adjustment)

Point Name	Sample Skewness
Gumara near Bahirdar	-0.044
Ribb near Adis Zemen	-0.068

[Source: ENTRO, 2010]

Table 10 summarizes the flood flows from the statistical analysis using both the LP3 and the EV1 distributions.

Table 10 Flood flow estimates using LP3 and EVI distributions

Station name	2-yr peak(CMS)	5-yr peak(CMS)	10-yr peak(CMS)	50-yr peak(CMS)	100-yr peak(CMS)
Ribb					
LP3	148	188	212	262	282
EV1	142	185	214	278	305
Gumara					
LP3	329	404	448	539	574
EV1	325	397	445	551	596

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

Figure 14 and 15 include a comparison of the LP3, EV1 and the station data for each river. The station data were plotted using the Weibull plotting position formula (*Chow et. al 1988*) as stated by ENTRO (2010).

Figure 14 Ribb peak flow probability plot

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

Figure 15 Gumara peak flow probability plot

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

An inspection of the plots in Figure 14 through Figure 15 show that the LP3 distribution provides a good fit to the observed data for the Gumara gauge, while the EVI distribution provides a better fit for the Ribb. Therefore, in selection of a frequency distribution for the flood risk mapping the LP3 and EVI distributions are used for Gumera and Ribb basins respectively. Concerns regarding the representativeness of the historical peak flows for the Ribb, and to some extent for the Gumera are, addressed in the comparison with frequency flows estimated using hydrologic simulation.

5.1.3 Lake Level Estimates using Log Pearson Type III Distribution

The available Lake Tana water level data were, also input into the PeakFQ program to fit a LP3 distribution and derive return period maximums. Because lake level varies slowly from day to day, no peaking factor adjustments are necessary. The sample skewness of the lake level data input into PeakFQ was 0.23. Lake level estimates derived using both the LP3 and EV1 distributions are shown in Table 11. Lake Tana level data were also analyzed and the results were found to be very similar between the two approaches.

Table 11 Lake level estimates using LP3 and EVI distributions

Probability Distribution	2-yr peak(CMS)	5-yr peak(CMS)	10-yr peak(CMS)	50-yr peak(CMS)	100-yr peak(CMS)
LP3	1787.22	1787.54	1787.73	1788.10	1788.24
EV1	1787.19	1787.51	1787.72	1788.19	1788.38

[Source: adopted from ENTRO, 2010]

5.2 Conclusions and discussions

In the Flood frequency analysis, a 50-year flow observation data were used to relate the magnitude of extreme events to their frequency of occurrence in different return periods. This means that, the number of observation is as long as half of the return periods that will be computed to insure that the computed flood frequency results are more reasonable for application. For instance, to estimate a 100-year flood we should have at least a 50 year observed time series data. Otherwise, predictions beyond a 100-year (say 200, 500 year) return period might not be good enough to get reliable results.

In general, the severity of the flood disasters has increased alarmingly since the mid of 1990's 1995/6 in Fogera area (ENTRO, 2010). However, flows show a decreasing trend, below the average value since 1980 disparate to the Gumara flows. There are different reasons for this apparent contradiction, such as the inaccuracy associated with the Ribb data and the fact that human activities driven by population growth have exacerbated flood risk. Therefore, the reason is highly likely due to high uncertainties associated with the data set i.e. more unreliable data is found or can be felt. In addition to this, may be due to some improper land use such as deforestation and poor agricultural practices, change of the river morphology and population growth in the area might aggravate the cause.

These problems would be, managed by taking into account many controlling measures such as improved land use policies, urban planning, improving and expansion of soil and water conservation and so on. However, the most important thing is encouraging of ground data measurements.

6 Hydrological modelling

In modelling theory the use of distributed parameters model either physically based or conceptual has become another increasingly popular way to address catchment and higher water level management. These models use many different parameters whose value varies widely in space and time (Kannan,et al., 2007).

SWAT is a distributed hydrologic model integrated with geographic information system (GIS) to simulate the hydrological processes and stream flows. This modelling system applied to the study area. In corresponding to different topography, soil types, and land use/cover classifications over the total catchment of 2736km², SWAT-GIS delineates the watershed based on 90-meter resolution DEM into eight simulation sub watersheds. Each watershed was, through a unique Hydrological Response Unit (HRU) that owns the similar hydrological characteristics. Figure16 underneath shows the rainfall-runoff relationship of the entire catchment of the study area with five rain gauge stations and two-river gauging stations. Hence, these are used as input data for the hydrological SWAT model calibration and validation. The model was, calibrated from the year 2000 through 2005 and was validated from 2006 through 2009.

Figure 16 Measured daily rainfall runoff relationship of the Fogera floodplain
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

6.1 Data Preparation using Arc GIS

The globally and freely available Digital Elevation model (DTM) was, used to build the SWAT model. The data was originally produced by NASA, Shuttle Radar Topographic mission (SRTM). The SRTM 90m DEMs have a resolution of 90m. This SRTM data was projected in to the coordinate system to fit the dataset of the study area in to a common geographical location/reference system.

6.2 Hydrological Modelling with arc SWAT

6.2.1 SWAT Model Set Up

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool is a river basin model that was developed for the USDA Agricultural Research Service, by Blackland Research Center in Texas (<http://www.brc.tamus.edu/blackland/>). The SWAT model is a widely known tool that has been used in several cases world-wide. SWAT has the ability to predict the impact of land management practices on water, sediment yield and agricultural chemical yield in large complex watersheds (Fohrer, *et al.*, 2001). The current study focuses only on the hydrological component of the model. What distinguishes SWAT from ordinary techniques used to estimate runoff is that it is a physical model. The model takes into account such data as climate, soil properties, topography, land cover and management, and produces outputs with the use of common hydrological equations. Apart from the ability to take into account land use and soil data, SWAT differs from other physical models in its ability to separate the watershed into sub-basins and Hydrologic Response Units (HRUs). The main basin is divided into smaller ones, by selecting points on the stream network that act as outlets. In this way, the model can provide output data, such as discharge at specific points of the river network. The partitioning of the basin or the sub basins in HRUs has the meaning of dividing the watershed into no more than 100 different areas, which have the same properties regarding land use and soil. The equations are applied in each HRU separately and surface runoff and ground water flow are routed to neighboring HRUs, up to the outlet of the basin (Arnold and Fohrer, 2005). The hydrologic component of SWAT is based on the following water balance equation:

$$SW_t = SW + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_i - Q_i - ET_i - P_i - QR_i)$$

Equation 1 Water balance equation

Where: SW_t is the final soil water content (mm), SW is the water content available for plant uptake, defined as the initial soil water content minus the permanent wilting point water content (mm), t is time in days, R is rainfall (mm), Q_i is surface runoff (mm), ET_i is evapotranspiration (mm), P_i is percolation (mm) and QR_i is return flow (mm). SWAT incorporates some of the most common hydrological equations for the simulation of flow. For the accurate implementation of these equations detailed input data are needed. Of significant value to the simulation are the digital elevation model (DEM) of the watershed, the soil and land use data and the climatic data of the area. The importance of land uses in the operation of the model lies mainly in the computation of surface runoff with the help of the SCS curve (Garg, *et al.*, 2011). The model includes in its database 102 different land use types, with each one assigned to a CNII value (Curve Number for hydrological condition II). The user is required to link each of the land uses that appear in the watershed to the ones that the model can identify. The success of the simulation depends highly on the accurate assignment of land uses.

6.2.2 Sensitive parameters

As discussed above the distributed models used in hydrological modelling have many parameters. To get a better and useful result every parameter is required to have sensitive value. Often calibration is undertaken to reduce model uncertainty associated with model parameters. Therefore, to insure efficient calibration a sensitivity analyses is

conducted to identify the most sensitive parameters. Accordingly, the ten most sensitive parameters for the two sub catchments are shown in Table 12 below.

Table 12 Sensitive parameters selected for model calibration

S/N	Parameters	Unit	Lower and upper bounds	Ribb Rank	Gumara Rank
1	ALPHA_BF	days	0 - 1	1	2
2	BLAI	m ² /m ²	0 - 1	7	9
3	CANMIX	mm	0 -10	9	8
4	CH_K2	mm/hr	0 -150	12	10
5	CH_N2	-	0 - 1	11	12
6	CN2	-	± 25	2	1
7	ESCO	-	0 - 1	3	4
8	GW_DELAY	days	-10 - 10	5	7
9	GW_REVAP	-	± 0.036	10	11
10	GWQMN	mm	0 - 5000	4	3
11	SOL_AWC	mm/mm	± 25%	8	6
12	SOL_Z	mm	± 25%	6	5

6.2.3 Model Calibration and Evaluation

Model calibration focuses on the detailed representation of the land use data in the watershed aiming in a more precise simulation of the hydrologic cycle, and in assessing the sensitivity of the model on land use information of varying detail. The present study employs 6 different land uses; these are (dry land, crop land, urban residential medium density, grassland, shrub land and savanna). Manual calibration of the model is a complex process requiring experimentation with multiple parameters that affect the precision of the simulation. All the way through adjustment of the parameterization, satisfactory simulation results were obtained for the two catchments with the accuracy of 0.4 and 0.60 for Nash-sutcliffe coefficient, 0.62 and 0.65 for correlation coefficient over the 6 years continuous simulations on daily discharges of the water cycle of the Ribb and Gumara catchments respectively. Regarding the simulation of this particular study, the calibration of the model proved to be quite satisfactory as compared to (Setegn, *et al.*, 2008) which reported that N_s is from 0.41 through 0.61 and Coefficient of determination (R^2) is from 0.57 through 0.71, and the results are shown in Figure 17 and 18. In addition to this, the simulated discharges were compared to the observed on a daily and monthly time step with the use of several indexes, and mainly the Nash & Sutcliffe coefficient. The Nash & Sutcliffe coefficient (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970) is an estimate of the variation of a time series from another, provided by the equation:

$$N_s = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{obs,i} - Q_{sim,i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_{obs,i} - \overline{Q_{sim}})^2}$$

Equation 2 The Nash & Sutcliffe coefficient

Where: Q_{sim} (m³/sec) is the simulated time series, Q_{obs} (m³/sec) the observed time series and $\overline{Q_{sim}}$ (m³/sec) the numerical mean for the simulated time series. A Nash & Sutcliffe coefficient approaching unity indicates that the estimated time series is almost identical to the observed one. In model calibration it should be noted that the warm-up period is essential for the stabilization of parameters (e.g groundwater depth). However, there is no warming-up period in the calibration process due to data limitation and high

uncertainty in the model. Therefore, the model is run for years 2000 to 2005. The N_s index reached the value of 0.72 for Gumara, signifying a quite precise calibration. The calibration accuracy was checked by calculating several other indexes, as well. These are the % difference between the total discharge of the simulated and the observed time series, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the correlation coefficient of the time series. The results of these tests proved to be quite satisfactory and are summarized in Table 13 below. Subsequently, the model was validated using the same indexes, for the period of January 2006 to December 2009, giving similar results to those of the calibration. The comparison of the simulated to the observed discharge for the model calibration and validation period is presented in Figure 17 and 19 for daily bases and Figure 18 and 20 for monthly bases. The resulting indexes are summarized in Table 13 and 14 below.

Figure 17 Gumara daily flow calibration and validation model result

Figure 18 Gumara monthly calibration and validation result

Rainfall Runoff (SWAT) Model Result

Figure 19 Ribb daily flow Calibration and validation model result

Figure 20 Ribb monthly calibration and validation result

Figure 21 Ribb and Gumara calibration of correlation result

Figure 22 Ribb and Gumara validation of correlation result

Table 13 Calibration statistical result

Catchment Name	Volume Percentile		RMSE		N _s		R ²	
	Error(D)		Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly
	Daily	Monthly						
Ribb	32	0.38	17	13	0.40	0.45	0.62	0.65
Gumara	-27	-0.26	34	24	0.60	0.72	0.65	0.80

Table 14 Validation statistical result

Catchment Name	Volume Percentile		RMSE		N _s		R ²	
	Error(D)		Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly
	Daily	Monthly						
Ribb	33	0.53	22	17	0.30	0.40	0.70	0.72
Gumara	-14	-0.05	45	24	0.60	0.75	0.65	0.76

6.2.4 Land use change scenarios

There are different factors affecting the runoff generation. One is the meteorological factors such as, rainfall intensity, rainfall amount, rainfall duration, and distribution over the drainage basin, direction of storm movement, and secondly is climatic conditions that affect evapotranspiration such as temperature, wind, relative humidity and so on. Thirdly, is the physical characteristics that affects the runoff generation, based on vegetation cover, soil type, drainage area, basin shape, elevation, topography, drainage network patterns, ponds, lakes, reservoirs, sinks, in the basin which prevent or delay runoff from continuing downstream. In addition to this, human activities can also greatly contribute to the runoff generation as part of land use change. As the number of human inhabitant increases the intervention also increase, and as more development and urbanization occurs, most of the natural landscape is replaced by impervious surfaces such as houses, roads that reduces infiltration into the ground and accelerates runoff to the ditches and streams. Accordingly, the following different scenarios of land use change are developed to see the effect of land use change in the study area.

Scenario A: Expansion of agricultural/cropland, According to this scenario, the agricultural land area has expanded by a percentage of about 30%, balanced by a decrease of grass and savanna land area, while urban and other areas have remained intact.

Scenario B: Expansion of dry land. According to this scenario, the dry land area has expanded by a percentage of about 30%, balanced by a decrease of grass and savanna land area, while urban and other areas have remained intact.

Scenario C: Expansion of urban areas. According to this scenario, the urban area has expanded by a percentage of about 30%, balanced by a decrease of grass and savanna land area, while other areas have remained intact.

The above three scenarios are summarized and presented in Table 15 below.

Table 15 Land use change scenario

Percentage of Area Change for Every Land Use%							
Scenario	Description	Urban	Dry land	Grass land	Shrub land	Savanna	Crop land
A	Expansion of agricultural land	0	-10	0	0	-20	30
B	Expansion of dry land	0	30	0	0	-30	0
C	Expansion of urban land	30	-10	0	0	-20	0

6.3 Results

In order to assess the effects of the land use changes suggested by the three scenarios, the new land use update DAT files depicting the land use patterns imported into SWAT, with the same set of parameters used in the original calibration. The execution of the model gave river discharge outputs that correspond to the new land use patterns. Then, the outputs compared to the ones of the baseline simulation. After this by estimating the percentages of discharge change for every scenario then this will be propagated to the flood frequency analyses. Finally, using these results ensemble simulation of Q_{100} was produced. Therefore, the result of each model run scenario is shown in Table16 and Figure 23 through 28 below.

Table 16 Land use change scenarios result result

Scenarios	River name	Q_{100} before LUP	Q_{100} Peaking factor	Q_{100} after LUP
A	Ribb	305	1.8	555
B	Ribb	305	1.6	488
C	Ribb	305	2.4	730
A	Gumara	574	1.3	746
B	Gumara	574	1.2	689
C	Gumara	574	1.9	1090

Figure 23 Ribb Model result land use change scenario-A

Figure 24 Ribb Model result land use change scenario-B

Figure 25 Ribb Model result land use change scenario-C

Figure 26 Gumara Model result land use change scenario-A

Figure 27 Gumara Model result land use change scenario-B

Figure 28 Gumara Model result land use change scenario-C

6.4 Conclusions and discussions

The method presented for quantifying the effects of land-use change on total runoff for the Fogera floodplain watershed in Ethiopia is the hydrological model SWAT and the land use change procedure introduced in SWAT 2009. Three different land use change scenarios were applied to the study basin and the discharge outputs were compared to the ones of the base run. All three scenarios gave an increase in discharge during wet months, and a decrease and increase during dry periods. The response of the basin to each scenario can be summarized in the following: by expanding the agricultural land over savanna and dray land by 30%, a mean monthly increase in the river discharge of up to 20% was observed from July to August and a respective reduction from January to June, reaching a maximum of 15% in June. The expansion of dry land in the basin that takes place according to scenario B resulted in substantial increases in mean monthly discharge of around 40% for wet months while during the summer discharge decreased

up to 35%. The final scenario of expansion of urban land by 30% over dry and savanna land, gave more or less similar results to the ones of the agricultural expansion scenario, with the difference of smaller reductions in discharge during the summer months, and a significant increase of 5 to 10% during the wet season. The Graph 29 below shows the extremes ranking of scenarios independently to one another.

Figure 29 Scenarios extremes ranking independently

7 Hydrodynamic flood modelling with HEC-RAS

HEC-RAS is a one-dimensional hydraulic model, which is capable of simulating water surface profile of steady and unsteady flow in natural and artificial channels. HEC-RAS solves De Saint-Venant equations with an algorithm based on the Preissmann implicit four-point finite scheme

7.1 Model setup

Setting up the HEC-RAS model either manually or with the processed GIS data. Hence, HEC-GeoRAS, which is an extension of ArcGIS tools specifically designed to processes geospatial data to be used by HEC-RAS, is used to set the Geometry file for the model as shown below in Figure 30 and 31. Once setting the geometry file, the data is exported to HEC-RAS. Consequently, the flow data and the boundary conditions are entered to the model in HEC_RAS. In addition to this, some edits are possible in the geometry file in HEC-RAS. For example, editing of the topographic data, riverbank stations, river cross-sections and so on. Finally, the model will run and export the model result back to HEC-GeoRAS to map the water surface inundation and depth.

Figure 30 HEC-GeoRAS Geometry file
[Source: adopted from SRTM]

Figure 31 Imported Geometry File in HEC-RAS

7.1.1 Boundary conditions

The upstream boundary conditions used were the flow discharge at Gumara and Ribb gauging stations to the channel reach. The time series flow hydrographs (see Figure 32 below) considered was from 3rd to 20th of August 2006 for both rivers. The figure indicates that later than 14th of August the peak flows are falling due to the changeable river flow patterns as well as the decrease of rainfall distribution. The downstream boundary conditions of these two rivers used were the time series level of Lake Tana. The lake level is taken from the gauge four times every day and averaged efficiently due to wave impacts on the lake surface. The minimum and the maximum lake levels yearly is 1783.5 m and 1787 m correspondingly amsl (MWEE) and Figure 32 shows the upstream and downstream boundary condition for the model set up.

Figure 32 Gumara and Ribb flows and Lake Tana water level source
[Source: adopted from MWEE]

7.1.2 Manning’s coefficient

The Manning’s roughness coefficient is one of the key parameters used to evaluate the hydrodynamic flood extent patterns. It is an index of resistance to flow in channel. This resistance comes from the interaction of different elements. Among these elements, some of them are particle size of streambed materials, channel alignment, bed configuration, channel obstructions, converging or diverging streamlines and so on. The land use of the study area is dominated by agriculture, vegetation, agro-pastoral and pastoral activities. The soil type is more of a clay nature especially in the channel beds. The quantitative effect of most of these factors is not determinable and must be, approximated subjectively with personal expertise. Hence, a different combination of Manning’s coefficient that describes the area is set up in order to find the optimal model fit and to compensate the uncertainty associated with DEM and other sources of uncertainties.

7.2 Flood inundation modelling

This study uses HEC-RAS, a one-dimensional hydraulic model that is capable to simulate water surface profile of steady and unsteady flow in natural and artificial channels. HEC-RAS solves De Saint-Venant equations with an algorithm based on the Preissmann implicit four-point finite scheme (Preissmann, 1961). The selection of 1D or 2D model depends on the purpose of the research and dimension of the model. A 2D model that solves other complex equations will bring about more data and parameter uncertainties. It is vital to eliminate various sources of uncertainties if the research purpose is to assess the applicability of SRTM DTM to support global flood mapping. Furthermore, a 1D model is far more efficient than a 2D model when

computation time is a key issue, particularly for large-scale models. While applied to waterway floodplains where 1D flow is Principal, HEC-RAS is able to produce results with a level of accuracy analogous to 2D models (*M. S. Horritt and Bates, 2002*). HEC-RAS is capable of making in the same way good predictions of inundated area as 2D model, whether calibrated against hydrometric data or flood extent of another event, compared with LISFLOOD-FP (a raster-based inundation model) and TELEMAC-2D (a distributed model solves 2D shallow water equations of free surface flow) (*M. S. Horritt and Bates, 2002*).

In the same way, simulation of steady state has fewer uncertainties of input data than unsteady state simulation. In view of the fact that, steady state only regard as one value of peak discharge at upstream boundary, it will symbolize the magnitude of this flood event and at the same time reduce uncertainties brought by the time series of unsteady state. For that reason, this research simulates the steady flow state by using a 1D HEC-RAS model.

7.2.1 Model calibration (August 14, 2006 flood)

In the 14th of August 2006, the Ribb and Gumara Rivers experienced a significant flood event and satellite imagery has been found in the specific date and year from MODIS. In the Fogera floodplain analyzed here, the return period for such an event was estimated with an exedence probability of two years from the flood frequency analyses. According to the findings, the maximum discharge of the 2006-flood event at Ribb is 112m /s and at Gumara is 359 m/s; these were set as the upstream boundary conditions for the 1D steady flow simulation. Correspondingly, the water levels of Lake Tana observed at the same time were set as the downstream boundary condition.

The model was, calibrated by comparing the flood extent of each cross section with the high water marks (from MODIS) in the aftermath of the August 2006 flood event. Different sets of Manning's n values are tested in order to get the best fit model. Given the homogeneous characteristics of the river reach, the potentially distributed Manning's n value were limited to one value for the channel and one for the floodplain (*Di Baldassarre, et al., 2009*). These values are ranged from 0.02 to 0.06 with the interval of 0.01 for the channel, and for the Manning's n values on floodplain, they are ranged from 0.06 to 0.16 with interval of 0.02. Therefore, there are 35 different combinations of Manning's n values and 35 simulations were made to find the optimal combination of Manning's coefficient. Apparently, those unrealistic Manning's n sets of which the one on the main channel is larger than the one on floodplain would be eliminated. This is due to the consensus that the roughness of riverbed is smaller than that of the floodplain since flow scours riverbed almost all the time to make it smooth.

7.2.2 Model performance

Model performance is a concept of where one model is evaluated against another based on the objective function set for model evaluation (*Werner, 2004*). The objective function can be set according to the purpose of the study. In this research MAE and Ns is set as the evaluating criteria of the model performance. In addition to this, performance is predominantly viewed from the concept of model reliability and this reliability can be articulated as the reciprocal to predictive uncertainty (*Werner, 2004*).

According to the above notions of model performance, reliability, and predictive uncertainty theories, the following Table 17 through Table 20 are set to evaluate the performance. As a result, a counter of objective function that explicitly expressed the model performance is shown in Figures 34, 35 and 37. Furthermore, the predictive uncertainty and reliability of the different parameters set is also shown in Figure 33 and Figure 36 below.

Table 17 Calibration results of the Ribb

Mean absolute Error [m]	Manning's n floodplain [unit less]	Manning's n channel [unit less]
2567.88	0.04	0.02
2556.71	0.06	0.02
2541.78	0.08	0.02
2521.13	0.10	0.02
2405.17	0.12	0.02
2396.40	0.14	0.02
2374.39	0.16	0.02
2350.48	0.04	0.03
2272.15	0.06	0.03
2260.66	0.08	0.03
2131.66	0.10	0.03
2211.18	0.12	0.03
2194.82	0.14	0.03
2176.39	0.16	0.03
2157.20	0.04	0.04
2131.66	0.06	0.04
2101.89	0.08	0.04
2084.13	0.10	0.04
2087.16	0.12	0.04
2063.67	0.14	0.04
2031.92	0.16	0.04
1995.55	0.04	0.05
1975.47	0.06	0.05
1998.10	0.08	0.05
1963.66	0.10	0.05
1926.10	0.12	0.05
1890.41	0.14	0.05
1868.00	0.16	0.05
1930.41	0.04	0.06
1889.49	0.06	0.06
1851.85	0.08	0.06
1813.21	0.10	0.06
1793.08	0.12	0.06
2272.15	0.14	0.06
2260.66	0.16	0.06

Hence, Table 18 model results show that the model with Manning's n for floodplain and channel equal to 0.16 and 0.06 respectively gives the minimum error model result. This high value is due to the fact that the Ribb model has a higher uncertain date set. As a

result, the model is trying to compensate the uncertainties associated with this data set aiming at meeting the target point of floodplain extent (flood mark) for this research work.

Table 18 Optimal Manning's n at each cross section of the Ribb

Cross sections	Manning's n floodplain	Manning's n channel
All	0.16	0.06

Table 19 Calibration results of the Gumara

Mean absolute Error	Manning's n floodplain	Manning's n channel
945.08	0.04	0.02
882.49	0.06	0.02
858.12	0.08	0.02
870.60	0.10	0.02
902.07	0.12	0.02
924.45	0.14	0.02
945.95	0.16	0.02
967.81	0.04	0.03
931.73	0.06	0.03
925.19	0.08	0.03
937.55	0.10	0.03
963.94	0.12	0.03
999.02	0.14	0.03
1045.76	0.16	0.03
981.61	0.04	0.04
956.83	0.06	0.04
945.74	0.08	0.04
970.26	0.10	0.04
1008.64	0.12	0.04
1053.42	0.14	0.04
1106.65	0.16	0.04
990.68	0.04	0.05
963.51	0.06	0.05
954.50	0.08	0.05
993.11	0.10	0.05
1030.52	0.12	0.05
1091.29	0.14	0.05
1148.45	0.16	0.05
998.80	0.04	0.06
968.65	0.06	0.06
967.86	0.08	0.06
1009.68	0.10	0.06
1047.29	0.12	0.06
1113.23	0.14	0.06
1173.82	0.16	0.06

Hence, the above model results show that the model with Manning's n for floodplain and channel equal to 0.08 and 0.02 respectively gives the minimum error model result. Therefore, these Manning coefficients were used to analyses the performance of the model as shown below in Table 20

Table 20 Optimal Manning's n at each cross section of Gumara

Cross sections	Manning's n floodplain	Manning's n channel
All	0.08	0.02

As a conclusion the calibration of the roughness parameter which, together with the geometry is considered to have the most important impact on predicting inundation extent and flow characteristics. Manning's roughness coefficients for the Gumara and Ribb rivers (Fogera floodplain) cannot be measured explicitly and must be determined through calibration. The idea of parameter uncertainty analysis estimation method (type of GLUE) is involved in this research work in quantification of the uncertain parameters and their propagation through to inundation predictions.

In this research the idea of calibrating Manning coefficient model packages focus basically on improving the performance of the model. One may pose a question how would possibly this work could be successful, but the answer is simple and tricky because the overall importance and meaning of calibration is to matchup the model result with the benchmark (in this case satellite imagery MODIS) through all possible ways. In other words calibration is the art of diplomacy between the model result and the benchmark by reducing all the possible uncertainties associated with the model. Therefore, in this case study the idea of calibration of Manning coefficient is done based on the principles and notions of improving the reliability of the model by reducing the uncertainties in the model using expertise judgment of all possibilities. Understanding of such uncertainty is very essential and update to improve flood forecasting, floodplain mapping and flood management.

The simulations of the hydraulic model is evaluated based on different sets of Manning coefficients set and run according to Table 17 and 19 that is at each model run the result is evaluated against the MODIS imagery of flood extent to meet the objective function to minimize the error and be able to produce a representative flood extent map by trying all the possible solution and this exhaustive search is done for the Ribb and Gumara rivers and floodplains.

Figur 33 and 36 below shows the uncertainties of parameters (Manning coefficient) of model result in hydrodynamic modelling (HEC-RAS) of different possible combination of the manning coefficient based on the knowledge and physics of the area versus the flood extent obtained from the satellite imagery product of MODIS in August, 2006. In general the idea of the parameter uncertainty performed in this case study is to show how one can deal with it in data poor areas and improve his/her model performance just by reducing the uncertainties and improving the reliability associated with the parameter (Manning coefficient) of his/her model.

Figure 33 Gumera Model with different combinations of Manning's n

Figure 34 Gumera Model MAE Contour of flood extent

Figure 35 Gumara Model Ns-Efficiency Error Contour

Figure 36 Ribb Model with different combinations of Manning's n

Figure 37 Ribb Model MAE Contour of flood extent

As highlighted above, the possible combinations of Manning’s coefficient bring about the domain of the model efficiency criteria. Hence, this clearly indicates how the model parameter uncertainty propagates throughout the model. Nevertheless according to Table 14 the optimal Manning’s n at each cross section is set to get the best-calibrated model. Therefore, the optimal calibrated model result on the bases set for the model performance criteria is shown in Table 21 below.

Table 21 Hydrodynamic model performance

Name	Model Performance Criteria	
	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency
Ribb	1793m	-0.01
Gumara	702m	0.86

7.2.3 Model validation (August 19, 2006 flood)

Satellite imagery has also been found for the same year, on 19th of August 2006, from MODIS. This, imagery is used for model validation. Therefore, the measured discharge at the Ribb and Gumara was 120m³/s and 340m³/s respectively. These were set as the upstream boundary condition for 1D steady flow simulation. Correspondingly, the water levels of Lake Tana observed at the same time were set as the downstream boundary condition. Accordingly, Figure 38 and Figure 39 shows the result of model validation and Table 22 shows the model validation results of the objective function.

Figure 38 Gumera hydrodynamic model validation result

Figure 39 Ribb hydrodynamic model validation result

Table 22 Hydrodynamic model performance validation result

Model Performance Criteria		
Name	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency
Ribb	1799	-0.01
Gumara	770m	0.71

7.3 Flood Inundation mapping

The extreme historical flood event on August 14, 2006 of the study area, with the magnitude of 112 and 359m³/s of the Ribb and Gumara correspondingly are considered. This inundation mapping aims at producing the 2006 year flood in the Fogera floodplain and Q₁₀₀ with the deterministic approach. The distance between two cross sections is determined by the equation introduced and discussed by Di Baldassarre (2009).

$$\Delta x \approx KB$$

Equation 3 Distance between cross sections

Where B = bank full surface width in (m) of the main channel; and k =constant (with recommended range from 10 to 20). In this case, k is selected as 10. And the bank full surface width is decided to be set as 100m after measuring from the ground and Google Earth.

$$\Delta x = KB = 10 * 100 = 1000 = 1km$$

The total length (L) of the river reach form the gauging station to the Lake Tana is about 29 and 35km for Ribb and Gumara correspondingly (MWEE). In total, the number of cross sections should be:

$$n = \frac{L}{\Delta x} = \frac{29}{1} = 29 \text{ and } \frac{35}{1} = 35$$

Equation 4 Number of cross sections

Actually, 42 and 35 cross sections are formulated finally, because more detailed information is expected to be obtained from the model. After several tests, large extended cross sections which cover the whole area of flood extends on floodplain are sketched and created a polygon as shown in Figure 40. Obviously, small cross section extension will lose part of the flood inundation area. This will give a bad presentation of a flood inundation map.

The magnitude of 112 and 359 m³/s is fed into the upstream boundary, and the corresponding lake elevation observed at the same time is put as the downstream boundary condition.

The steady flow state is simulated and 1D model results are obtained in the form of water surface elevation and inundation width for each cross-sectional cut line. Bounding Polygon features are created based on the extension of cross section cut lines (Figure31). Inundation mapping is performed using the water surface elevations on the

cross-sectional cut lines feature class and is limited to bounding polygon features by ArcGIS. And floodplain delineation requires digital terrain model is completed.

Figure 40 Floodplain polygon

Figure 41 August 14, 2006 Flood Model result

Figure 42 Gumara flood event Q₁₀₀

Figure 43 flood event under land use change of urbanization of Q₁₀₀

The above Figures starting from Figure 41 through Figure 43 shows the deterministic flood inundation map of Gumera River for different flood events without considering the effect of hydraulic structures. The minimum water depth is set as 0.5m. This will help to eliminate the noise generated by the model. Hence, Figure 43 shows the deterministic flood inundation map of the Ribb and Gumera after urbanization. The Ribb river deterministic flood maps and the other scenarios are shown in Appendix-D.

Furthermore, a question of whether the flood area is increasing or decreasing according to the scenarios developed in chapter six is going to be discussed. Therefore, these results are, shown in Table 23 below for all the scenarios.

Table 23 Comparison of inundation area

Description	Unit	Baseline inundation area	Scenarios inundation areas	Percentage of increase with respect to flooding
Scenario A	m ²	95913231	145015679	51%
Scenario B	m ²	95913231	136842543	43%
Scenario C	m ²	95913231	162236089	69%

7.4 Conclusions and discussions

The above results show more or less reasonable results for the comparisons of different flood events. However, in low flow period, some noises are observed and this is one of the indications of SRTM DTM data uncertainty and the limitations of 1D model. Regardless of this analogous this data set of model building is still important in areas where data is so limited or highly uncertain, because, when one uses 2D or some other more detailed physical model in areas with the data of high uncertainty then this may bring about a big error to the model. Therefore, it is quite advisable to use simple models in areas where data are limited.

The Fogera floodplain modelling is concerned to Figure out how devastating the effect of land use change is and how useful the satellite imageries are. Accordingly it might be, concluded that the expansion of dry and, agricultural land and urbanizations has a serious impact in facilitating the devastating nature of flooding in the area. On the other hand, the aim of this inundation maps is to show how the satellite imageries are good enough to represent the model result. As a result, the Gumera hydrodynamic model shows a good performance with the imagery while the Ribb model fails to catch the imagery. However, with high flows the Ribb model captured the imagery. This situation clearly shows the role of uncertainty within the input data set. Hence, one cannot conclude that the uncertainty is entirely attributed to imagery but also with the inflow and SRTM DTM data set. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude from the study that different source of uncertainty are affecting the model result and then researches that is more robust is needed to evaluate the satellite imageries and the SRTM DTM data set.

Finally yet importantly, the model gave the anticipated result for the land use change as shown in Table 23 above. Thus, these scenarios confirm that if the land use changes to urban, agriculture and/or expansion of dry land more discharges are yielded. These will lead to with more flooding while; there is a scene during the dry season reduces the discharge.

8 Ensemble simulation

8.1 General objective and model setup

The ensemble simulation endeavors at evaluating and weighing the model performances when uncertainty is considered. In this research to weigh up the performance by analyzing how inflow uncertainties propagate through the model. The basis for choosing inflow as the main source of uncertainty is that, generally speaking, inflow is one of the most second important factors that affect hydraulic model results (Pappenberger, et al., 2007). The first most important factor typically is the Manning's n on the channel and floodplain. In view of the fact that the influence of Manning's n on channel and floodplain has been analyzed during model calibration and model validation, inflow data uncertainty is considered here. Moreover, design flood is very uncertain since it is evaluated based on the measured data by statistic methods. At the very beginning, there are uncertainties in the measured data due to low measuring instruments accuracy, careless surveyors, lack of education, not understanding of data importance etc. Following, there are also uncertainties in the statistical methods. Taken as a whole, the design flood uncertainty will be augmented by the two sources of uncertainties mentioned above. The ensemble simulation is performed to the Ribb and Gumara Rivers, using the HEC-RAS model calibrated and validated against 2006 flood event. Hence, a Monte Carlo Simulation based on the GLUE (Generalized likelihood uncertainty estimation) framework is chosen as the way or tool to analyze uncertainty. Thus the GLUE methodology embraces the notion of *equifinality*, where several parameter sets can turn out equally good model predictions the level of uncertainty in model predictions can also be controlled by rejecting poorer simulations (MS Horritt, 2006). For that reason, 200 inflow discharges are generated according to a normal distribution. The normal distribution with lower and upper bounds are assumed to present the variation of inflow discharge. The mean value of normal distribution is selected as 305 and 574 m^3/s for the Ribb and Gumara correspondingly. It is the discharge of once in a hundred years flood exceedance (ENTRO, July 2010). This value is greater than the discharge value on which the model is calibrated (112 and 359 m^3/s for the Ribb and Gumara respectively). This would increase the simulation accuracy since the 1D hydraulic models calibrated on high magnitude event will have a better performance on simulating another similar high magnitude event. The value of the lower and upper for the Ribb and Gumara (90,135) and (288,431) are set as bounds of the normal distribution, respectively. They are calculated by $112 \pm 20\%$ and $359 \pm 20\%$. These 200 single-value discharges were fed as the upstream boundary condition for a steady state ensemble simulation. Other configurations of the original model which have been calibrated against the 2006 flood event have remained the same.

8.2 Methodology

For both the Ribb and the Gumara model, 200 water profiles are simulated. Among the 200 simulated results, the water profiles of the 5th through 95th percentile results will be chosen for further analyses of their water profile. The steps are described below. These stapes are basically based on the Monte Carlo simulation techniques. In hydrodynamic 1D modeling, there is a fair amount of uncertainty and risk involved with estimating the future value of Figures or amounts due to the wide variety of potential outcomes. Monte

Carlo simulation (MCS) is one technique that helps to reduce the uncertainty involved in estimating future outcomes. MCS can be applied to complex, non-linear models or is used to evaluate the accuracy and performance of other models. In short, MCS is a technique that converts uncertainties in input variables of a model into probability distributions. By combining the distributions and randomly selecting values from them, it recalculates the simulated model many times and brings out the probability of the output. In addition to this the propagation of the uncertain bound of inflow (input of MCS results) to the model is also shown at some selected cross sections versus the likelihood of flood extent.

The method is consists of the following structures.

1. Based on GLUE, each simulation result (flood extent at each cross section) has to be assigned to a likelihood weight, and each weight has to be rescaled to the summation of one. Normal/Gaussian Distribution is chosen, because it is a continuous distribution applied in situations where the mean and the standard deviation are given and the mean represents the most probable value of the variable. It is symmetrical around the mean and is not bounded

2. Consider that we have a real-valued function $g(X)$ with probability frequency function $P(x)$ (if X is discrete), or probability density function $f(x)$ (if X is continuous). Then we can define the expected value of $g(X)$ in discrete and continuous terms respectively

$$E(g(x)) = \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) \cdot P(x), \text{ where } P(x) > 0 \text{ and } \sum_{-\infty}^{\infty} P(x) = 1$$

Equation 5 Expected outcome of MCS discrete

$$E(g(x)) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) \cdot f(x) dx, \text{ where } f(x) > 0 \text{ \& } \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx = 1$$

Equation 6 Expected outcome of MCS continues

3. make n random drawings of X ($x_1, \dots, x_n$), called trial runs or simulation runs, calculate $g(x_1), \dots, g(x_n)$ and find the mean of $g(x)$ of the sample:

$$g_x^U(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(x_i)$$

Equation 7 MCS estimator

Thus, represents the final simulation value of $E(g(x))$

$$\text{As } n \rightarrow \infty, g_x^U(x) \rightarrow E(g(x))$$

Thus, it is able to compute the dispersion around the estimated mean with the unbiased variance of $g_x^U(x)$.

Thus calculated as below

$$\text{Var}(g_n^U(x)) = \frac{1}{n} \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n [(g(x_i) - g_n^U(x))]^2$$

Equation 8 Unbiased variance

4. The next step is to start the Monte Carlo simulation - a value from each distribution is randomly picked and is recalculated many times, each time using a different combination of values for the input discharge, until the input variable fits normal distribution.

5. Finally, it can also add different charts in the analysis of the results for illustration. The frequency chart, for instance, the distribution in Figure 44 and 45 below shows explicitly the degree of uncertainty in the input variables, and how often they occur.

All the above steps are achieved using a Monte Carlo tool in the excel program. The following Figure 44 and Figure 45 are the result of 1000000 trials of the Monte Carlo simulation for the Gumara and Ribb respectively.

Figure 44 Gumara degree of input variables uncertainty

Figure 45 Ribb degree of input variables uncertainty

8.3 Result

The model gives results in each cross section. These are the 200 values of flood extent which are the results of each simulation. These data sets are sorted from small to large and the first and last 5 values are eliminated. Thus, 90 values that represent 5% to 95% percentile are obtained. Histograms which present the number of values located in certain equally distributed intervals of flood extent are made. A polynomial trend line fits for each histogram was produced, which can give an idea of how the distribution of flood extent for one cross section looks like (in this case, it is the No.15 and 35 cross section) see Figure 47, 48. Both two polynomial trend lines show that the distribution is somewhat close to the normal distribution. The distribution does not vary surprisingly from a normal distribution. It is an approximately normal distribution. This shows how input uncertainty is not highly propagated through the model. Even though, a 1D hydraulic model is a nonlinear system (less parameters), however the transformation of the input uncertainty is somehow linear transformation. Therefore, it can be concluded that a linear transformation can also happen in a 1D hydraulic model.

After having these results an error and model performance counters are produced. This clearly shows which model works well and with what efficiency. In addition to this, the graphs of each flood extent model results obtained from the ensemble simulation show how the model uncertainty is propagated throughout the model (Figure 46 and 51). In addition to this, Figure 46 and 51 also shows input predictive uncertainty and reliability. Figure 49, 50 and 54 below shows the model performance under input predictive uncertainty.

Figure 46 Gumara ensemble simulation model result

Gumera flood extent simulation histogram

Figure 47 Gumera flood extent distribution model result at cross section 15

Figure 48 Gumera flood extent distribution model result at cross section 35

Figure 49 Gumara MAE couture of ensemble simulation

Figure 50 Gumara Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency ensemble simulation

Figure 51 Ribb ensemble simulation model result

Figure 52 Ribb flood extent distribution model result at cross section 15

Figure 53 Ribb flood extent distribution model result at cross section 35

Figure 54 Ribb ensemble simulations MAE counter

8.4 Conclusion and discussion

Considering the purpose of flood inundation modeling, which is to produce inundation maps for the Ribb and Gumara rivers, the anticipated precision is more or less sufficient to the purpose of planning or forecasting. Therefore, a conclusion can be made: for large magnitude flood events, 1D hydraulic modeling using SRTM DTM topography data is acceptable and fitting. Although, the resolution of topography has quite large deviation 90m for SRTM, the ensemble simulation results of the Gumara river do not have large errors between the model result and satellite imagery while results for the Ribb river have a big error. This shows the influence of topography and 1D model in hydraulic modeling and of course the satellite imagery uncertainty is still there. On the other hand, there is a good model performance in the case of the Gumara river. The reason is that the calibrated Manning's n of the SRTM DTM Model compensates the uncertainties brought by the topography and other data source of uncertainty. In theory there is a consensus that says there is only one true value of Manning's n for one location and it should not be calibrated as it represents the physical world. However, the objective is to build a consistent model with a fair prediction power. In the end, the model simulation results should match the measurements. Furthermore, the Manning's coefficients are distributed and it is tricky to get the true values. For that reason, Manning's coefficients were treated as the model parameters here and they could be calibrated to minimize the objective function.

9 Probabilistic flood inundation mapping

9.1 General description

As highlighted in the literature review, probabilistic flood inundation maps are extremely important and fitting having added value to deterministic flood inundation maps since the previous type represents various uncertainties in the hydraulic models. Moreover, the selected inundation model does not have to be a fully distributed 2D model. Thus, a simple 1D hydraulic model jointly with GIS technology is competent to put into practice this probabilistic approach for producing flood inundation map. Furthermore, a 1D HEC-RAS model which can give the water surface elevation and flood extent width at each cross section is able to run a large number of simulations to envelop the possible inflows as the hydrological input. Finally yet importantly, a simple model based on SRTM DTM has a reasonable performance for producing the flood inundation maps (Yan, 2011).

9.2 Fogera Wereda Probabilistic flood inundation mapping

This case study aims at reproducing the 2006 flood in Fogera floodplain with the probabilistic approach. Hence, the extreme historical flood event on August 14, 2006 of the study area, with the magnitude of 112 and 359m³/s of Ribb and Gumara correspondingly under uncertainty bound $\pm 20\%$ as well as Q_{100} of the same uncertainty bound is considered. Following, producing the deterministic flood inundation maps as discussed earlier in Chapter 7, a probabilistic inundation map is produced according to the three steps for producing probabilistic flood inundation map described by (Stephens, et al., 2011). As described above, this flood map takes into account model uncertainties. There is no historical data for carrying out sensitivity analysis to find out the most uncertain source. Thus, inflows are assumed to be the source of uncertainty. Ensemble simulations with 200 runs are executed. After ensemble simulation, the next step is to implement a visualization technology, which transform or combine 200 inundation maps to one inundation map with probability. The equations and algorithms for achieving this with a simple raster-based model are introduced as follows: first, the model simulated results of flood extent were compared with satellite image. Using the equation below set as evaluation criteria for model performance.

$$M_p = \frac{N_s}{N_{s(max)}} \quad \text{Or} \quad M_p = \frac{MAE_{(min)}}{MAE} \quad \text{if } MAE = 0 \text{ then } M_p = 1$$

Equation 9 Model performance

Where $MAE_{(min)}$ is the flooded area predicted by the model with the minimum mean absolute error, MAE is the predicted mean absolute error of each simulation; M_p is the model performance so as to give weight to each run. After a large number of runs different Model performances are obtained and their corresponding flood maps are produced. Before these maps are combined together, each map has to be assigned weights which represent the likelihood. This approach is based on the GLUE (Generalize likelihood uncertainty estimation) framework (Aronica, et al., 2002). This weight, L_i , ranged from 0 to 1, is formulated by the equation below:

$$L_i = \left[\frac{Mp_i - \min(Mp_i)}{\max(Mp_i) - \min(Mp_i)} \right]$$

Equation 10 Model performance weight

After this to normalize L_i the formula below is introduced.

$$L_i = \left[\frac{Mp_i - \min(Mp_i)}{\max(Mp_i) - \min(Mp_i)} \right] * \left[\frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n Mp_i} \right]$$

Equation 11 Weight normalization

Where $\max(Mp_i)$ and $\min(Mp_i)$ are the maximum and minimum measures of fit found throughout the ensemble and n is number of simulations. It can be seen from the equation above that the bigger the measure of fit, which means the more accurate the prediction, the bigger the weight will be assigned to the simulation. After obtaining the weight for each simulation, the focus will be set on the flood situation for each cell, and the weighted average flood state for each cell will be made:

$$C_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n L_i * W_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^n L_i}$$

Equation 12 Weighted average for each cell

Where C_j is an indication of weighted average flood state for j^{th} cell, W_{ij} is the flood situation for j^{th} cell in simulation i , which is $W_{ij} = 0$ for not been inundated and $W_{ij} = 1$ for been inundated. And C_j is ranged from 0 to 1, which represents the likelihood of flood state of a particular cell for a typical flood event. The following graphs from Figure 55 through Figure 58 shows the model performance and the weights given to each simulation. Therefore, the high performance gets the highest weight of the ensemble.

Figure 55 Gumara model performance counter

Figure 56 Gumara model normalized weights counter

Figure 57 Ribb model performance counter

Weights (Li)

Figure 58 Ribb model normalized weights counter

In order to produce the probabilistic inundation map, which takes into account the uncertainty of peak inflow, a simple approach was applied referring to the results reported in (Di Baldassarre, *et al.*, 2009). According to these findings, 200 normal distributed of 1000,000 Monte Carlo simulation results in the range of $112 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} \pm 20\%$ for 2006 flood event and $359 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} \pm 20\%$ for the 2006 flood event peak flow of the Ribb and Gumara respectively were used as the upstream boundary condition for the ensemble simulation. In addition to this 1000,000 Monte Carlo simulation results in the range of $305 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} \pm 20\%$ for Q_{100} flood event and $574 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} \pm 20\%$ for Q_{100} flood event of Ribb and Gumara respectively were also used as the upstream boundary condition for the ensemble simulation. Corresponding lake level estimates using LP3 and EVI distributions were also adopted for the downstream boundary condition. Therefore, Figure 59 Figure 60 below shows the probabilistic map of the Gumera and Ribb rivers for different flood events.

Figure 59 Probabilistic map of Gumera 2006 flood event

Figure 60 Probabilistic map of Ribb Q₁₀₀ flood event

Furthermore this research is also aiming at reproducing the probabilistic inundation maps under land use change scenarios. Thus the flow results under land use change scenarios for Q_{100} are also adopted as upstream boundary condition in the range of $\pm 20\%$ peak flow of each scenario. Based on the results of these scenarios the same principle of Monte Carlo sampling technique is used to sample 200 normal distributed values. The following Table 24 shows the flow of each scenarios as well as their upper and lower bounds. Finally three different deterministic and probabilistic inundation maps will be produced according to the scenarios.

Table 24 Land use change scenarios input uncertainty bound

River Name	Scenario	SWAT Model Result	Flow	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Ribb	A	555	444	666
Ribb	B	503	402	603
Ribb	C	730	584	876
Gumara	A	746	597	895
Gumara	B	689	551	827
Gumara	C	1090	872	1308

The whole procedure discussed above is achieved by ArcGIS together with HEC-GeoRAS. First, 200 ensemble inundation maps were imparted together to their 21 percentiles. The next step is to reclassify the grids. The grids with the inundation depth which is smaller than 0.5m were set to 0. This is to eliminate the noise generated by the model. And of course the grids with 'no data' were also set to no data. This 'no data' means there is no water in that grid, so the model did not take it in to account.

The third step is adding all the 21 reclassified inundation maps together using 'Raster Calculator' in ArcGIS. Subsequently a map with grids of value ranged from 0 to 21 is generated. The fourth step, based on the equation of C_j , is that the final value of each grid is calculated by the value generated by step three divided by 21. This is achieved by 'stretch' in ArcGIS by labeling the value of 0 to 0%, the value of 21 to 100%. The other values were interpolated in between. Finally, the probabilistic inundation maps of the 2006 year flood, Q_{100} , and Q_{100} of the three scenarios are produced in the Figures below (Figure 62 through Figure 67).

The green grids present places which are least probable in this flood event, whereas red grids show places which have high probability to be inundated (up to 100%). The more reddish the color, the higher probability a grid will be inundated as shown in Figure 59 and 60 above.

According to the above scenarios a set of Monte Carlo sampling techniques of flow simulations is prepared for the input ensemble simulations of the above scenarios. Therefore, the following histograms shown in Figure 61 are the result of Monte Carlo sampling simulation techniques. These Figures help to show the distributions of input uncertainty in the model build up for the three scenarios.

Figure 61 Scenarios Monte Carlo simulation graphs

The scenarios of the Monte Carlo simulations are set as upstream boundary condition of the model and the lake level once in hundred years from lake frequency analyses in Table 11 of Chapter 5 is also set as downstream boundary condition. Therefore, the result of each simulation is shown from Figure 62 through Figure 67 and is discussed below.

Figure 62 Probabilistic map of Ribb scenario-A flood event

Figure 63 Probabilistic map of Gumera scenario-A Flood event

Figure 64 Probabilistic map of Rib scenario-B flood event

Figure 65 Probabilistic map of Gumera scenario-B flood event

Figure 66 Probabilistic map of Ribb scenario-C flood event

Figure 67 Probabilistic map of Gumera scenario-C flood event

9.3 Conclusions and discussions

These probabilistic maps are very useful or informative in the decision making process. Firstly, they display the probability of flood inundation rather than spuriously a precise flood extent (binary) map. Secondly, these maps considered the parameter and input (flow) uncertainties to describe the floodplain. This means that they took in to account the most significant source of uncertainty. Therefore, this method is relevant for producing the flood hazard maps for vulnerable areas especially in areas like Ethiopia where data is so limited and highly uncertain. Finally, even though these probabilistic maps do not produce a flood risk map they represent as a general the probability of the area to be flooded according to the weights given to the model performance.

The other main important point to be noted is that the probability estimate is dependent on the quality and quantity of data used to estimate the maps. Therefore, to reduce the level of uncertainty in the model result, it is needed to increase the quality of the data while building the model.

In general, the result maps of simulations of different scenarios and the baseline run developed in this research provides very useful information about the dynamics of the possible flooding.

From the above discussions it can be concluded that flood inundation probability as a proxy for hazard is appropriate. Specifically, in areas with poor or scarce data set this could give an alarm and priority set for decision makers and creates awareness for the inhabitants of the area.

Finally, the steps to produce the probabilistic maps are discussed below.

1. Set all outputs of hydrological models of the flood event of 2006, Q_{100} , and scenarios under land use change
2. Make a Monte Carlo simulation/sampling technique of each model result in step 1
3. Feed the results of step 2 into the hydrodynamic model to make an ensemble simulation under parameter and input uncertainty.
4. Compare the flood extent result of step 3 with the satellite imagery and evaluate the model performance of each simulation.
5. Give weights for each ensemble simulation based on step 4. This will be an attribute to give higher weight to the best simulation/model performance of the ensemble simulation (type of GLUE methodology). Therefore there will not be equal likelihood to the probabilistic map to be reproduced.
6. Produce inundation map for each ensemble simulation
7. Reclassify the inundation maps in step 6
8. Multiply each reclassified maps by their corresponding weight
9. Sum up all the maps in step 8
10. Finally stretch all the summed up maps between 0 through 100 so as to make a probabilistic map of that particular event.
11. Repeat step 1 through 10 to reproduce probabilistic maps of different land-use scenarios.

10 Conclusions and recommendations

10.1 Conclusions

Flooding is a serious issue in the study area where it happens almost every year. The current climate and land use changes seem to have also played some role to the frequency of flooding in the area. One of the main tasks of this study was to evaluate how important/useful are the globally and freely available remote sensing data (TRMM, SRTM, MODIS) in developing countries.

This research work carried out an ensemble simulation of Fogera floodplain inundation under different sources of uncertainty. In particular, parameter and input uncertainty was explicitly taken into account and visualized via floodplain maps using HEC-RAS, Hec-GeoRAs, and GIS applications. Also, to simulate scenarios of land-use changes, two hydrological models (SWAT) for continuous simulation were developed for both the Ribb and Gumara catchments.

To this end, while the rainfall data from 2000 through 2006 were adopted from the previous research (*Assefa, et al., 2008*), rainfall data from 2007 through 2009 as well as flow data from 1959 through 2009 were collected from MWEE.

TRMM rainfall estimates were used to fill the significant data gaps in this study area. The comparison of ground data and TRMM data was based on visual interpretation of the time series of daily rainfall, as well as linear regression between the time series pairs. As a result, TRMM data source showed a better correlation than the relation between some of the ground data (*Assefa, et al., 2008*).

The SWAT application produced a reasonably good performance (Ns up to 0.75) taking into account the concept of the distributed model during the simulation period. However, this study also indicated that seasonality (wet and dry seasons), special distributions of rainfall and soil and land cover heterogeneity are a source of errors in hydrological models. Therefore, this analogous may lead to the significance of developing a seasonal parameterisation technique of model building. Thus, each simulation of the year is divided into two and then two parameter sets are obtained for each dry and wet period.

After the development of a well-calibrated SWAT model a new land use update was performed. The new module introduced in SWAT 2009 achieved this new land use update. While doing this, the percentage difference of the discharge response before and after the land use update of the specific date was assumed as the percentage increase or decrease of the flood frequency analyses. Therefore, if the current land use is changed to the new updated one then the discharge of Q_{100} of the flood frequency is multiplied by a factor (found by comparing simulations before and after land use change) and these reproduces a new Q_{100} for that specific land use (scenario) and see its effect via floodplain maps.

The hydrodynamic model HEC-RAS was developed for the Ribb and Gumara catchments using SRTM DTM as topographic input. A low and a high flow analyses was, conducted to evaluate errors and model uncertainty. The model for the Gumara

produced a good performance (MAE= 702m, $N_s=0.86$) taking in to consideration different combinations of the Manning's coefficient, while the model for the Ribb fails to capture a good performance (MAE=1799, $N_s=-0.01$).

The application of SRTM DTM with HEC-RAS, HEC-GeoRAS and GIS for producing probabilistic map was found to be a good and time saving technique for these data poor areas. However, especially for the Ribb, it fails to predict a flood event of different magnitude. This may be attributed mainly to the unreliability of the data set in the Addis Zemen gauging station and secondly, to the input (topography) and model structure uncertainty i.e. 1D is unable to simulate some 2D floodplain dynamics. Thus, a simple 2D model might be more appropriate. Regardless of these constraints, still SRTM DTM with HEC-RAS, Hec-GeoRAs and GIS application might produces a more reasonable probabilistic map for the reason that it weigh up model with high performance and weigh down model with less performance to show decision makers the significance of flood disasters and start setting priorities in data poor areas.

In this research work, the Monte Carlo simulation random value sampling was used. This technique helps to estimate the uncertainty associated to model predictions. Accordingly, the output of the input uncertainties has more or less similar pattern of the uncertainty propagation.

The results of scenarios of land use change have shown the same as the expectation in a general framework. However, the way the model structure computes has still some discrepancies of the study area.

The result of this research shows the applicability of ensemble simulation techniques, providing satisfactory outcomes for high flow conditions in the Ribb.

Flood risk mitigation is vital in developing countries. In the case of the Ethiopia, reducing flood risk is dependent upon alleviating poverty, and vice versa. Lack of food reduces human beings competence to cope with disasters, stresses and shocks. In addition to this, it means that unnecessary costs are not invested in areas with less probability of flood excedence and vice versa. Hence, this research will contribute to the efforts being under taken in the country for achieving the disaster prevention and protection policy of the government.

10.2 recommendations

10.2.1 General recommendations

- Using only one data source of remote sensing data is not an appropriate way to evaluate model performance. Additional validation data and measures of model robustness should be carried out. This would assist more to reduce the high uncertainty of the ground gauging, satellite imagery, SRTM DTM and flood mark data. Therefore, this might be achieved with increased use of satellite data.
- It is advisable to exercise different uncertainty estimation techniques to see different impacts on the outcome. This might help to improve or compare model reliability under uncertainties propagated throughout the model. Alternative techniques, such as MLUE or DREAM, might be utilized.
- The hydrodynamic model calibration and validation method, which was based on the use of satellite imageries only, might not be sufficient to evaluate the model performance. It is then recommended to test the model using high water marks measured on the ground by using appropriate measure of fit.
- The value of SRTM DTM topography data sets for producing probabilistic map should be tested in data rich areas where a comparison with more accurate topographies can be performed.

10.2.2 Specific recommendations

- For future research in the study area it is recommended to develop a land use model structure that gives an account of the dynamic process of the land use change. This model structure attributes the socio-economic as well as biophysical circumstances.
- For the hydrological modeling in the study area it is recommended to use other input data. Sources such as the ECMWF products of ERA interim and the, Family Early warning product RFE may improve the model performance and might help reduce predictive uncertainties in the model.
- The parameters used in building the hydrological SWAT model are derived from calibration with initial conditions extracted from the general guidelines that corresponds to the soil, land use and DEM of the area. However, the parameters are kept constant during the simulation period. Therefore, the extreme differences between the dry and the wet seasons in areas specially, like Ethiopia has a great influence. Hence, this common sense fact will lead us to recommend a seasonal parameterization.
- It is good to compare the results of this study with the simple raster models. For example, LISFLOOD-FP (Bates and De Roo, 2000). This consists of a one-dimensional kinematic wave approximation for channel flow solved using an explicit finite difference scheme and a two-dimensional diffusion wave representation of floodplain flow.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix-A Peaking factor plots and final peak factor adjusted peak flow time series

Appendix-B SWAT Soil class definition

Appendix-C Flow comparison before and after LUP with ranking base simulation

Appendix-D Model efficiency measurements criteria formulas

Appendix-E Ribb and Gumara Catchment Characteristics

Appendix-F Inundation maps of different model results

Appendix-G River cross-sections at gauging stations

Appendix-A Peaking factor plots and final peak factor adjusted peak flow time series

Gumara

Ribb

Adjusted Peak Flow Time Series

Appendix-B SWAT Soil class definition

Appendix-C Flow comparison before and after LUP with ranking base simulation

Appendix-D Model efficiency measurements criteria formulas

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (q_{sim,i} - q_{obs,i})^2} \quad r^2 = \frac{\left[\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{si} - \bar{q}_s)(q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o) \right]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{si} - \bar{q}_s)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o)^2}$$

$$E_{Ns} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - q_{si})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (q_{oi} - \bar{q}_o)^2} \quad D = 100 * \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n q_{si} - \sum_{i=1}^n q_{oi} \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^n q_{oi}} \right]$$

Appendix-E Ribb and Gumara Catchment Characteristics

Basin characteristics

Subbasin	Area (ha)	ElevMin	ElevMax
1	73898.21	1793.00	3167.00
2	21919.45	1884.00	3040.00
3	44832.00	1885.00	4109.00
4	20378.49	1886.00	2849.00
5	43.25	1886.00	1903.00
6	24077.81	1794.00	2485.00
7	38954.81	1886.00	3704.00
8	43536.14	1886.00	2749.00

Land use Characteristics

VALUE	COUNT	OID_	ObjectID	Areaper	LUSwat
1	242	0	0	0.077	URMD
2	100575	1	1	31.869	CRDY
6	29941	2	2	9.487	CRWO
7	1452	3	3	0.460	GRAS
8	594	4	4	0.188	SHRB
10	182780	5	5	57.918	SAVA

Slope Characteristics

VALUE	COUNT	OID_	SlopeLo	SlopeHi	SlopeClass	SlopeName
1.00	15067.00	1.00	0.00	1.50	1.00	0-1.5
2.00	46815.00	2.00	1.50	5.00	2.00	1.5-5
999.00	253702.00	3.00	5.00	9999.00	999.00	5-9999

Appendix-F Inundation maps of different model results

2006 flood event deterministic map

Q100 deterministic inundation map

Scenario-A deterministic inundation map

Scenario-B deterministic inundation map

Scenario-C KMZ file

Appendix-G River cross-sections at gauging stations

